

Review

Available data and knowledge gaps of the CESAR1 solvent system

Diego Morlando^a, Vanja Buvik^b, Asmira Delic^b, Ardi Hartono^a, Hallvard F. Svendsen^a, Hanne M. Kvamsdal^b, Eirik F. da Silva^b, Hanna K. Knuutila^{a,*}

^a Department of Chemical Engineering, NTNU, NO-7491 Trondheim, Norway

^b SINTEF Industry, NO-7465 Trondheim, Norway

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ABSTRACT

Amine-based chemical absorption stands out as the leading technology for post-combustion CO₂-capture. A blend of 3 M 2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMP) and 1.5 M piperazine (PZ), also known as CESAR1, has proven to outperform the current benchmark ethanolamine (MEA), exhibiting better energy performance and lower degradation rates. This review aims to gather all the experimental laboratory and pilot available data for CESAR1 and its constituent components. Experimental gaps to develop reliable process models are detected and future experiments are proposed. An overview of the knowledge related to amine and degradation compound emissions and environmental impacts of CESAR1, together with hands-on experience in operating the solvent, is presented in this review.

The main findings of the review are that sufficient physical properties, N₂O-solubility, and speciation data for the CESAR1 solvent are not available in the open literature, even though necessary for the development of reliable process models. A review of the degradation compounds for AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ blends outlines that the nitrogen balance for AMP and PZ is not closed, meaning that there still are compounds that need identification and quantification in the degraded solvent. Given the higher volatility of AMP compared to MEA, a better understanding of the formation and behaviour of aerosol and gas phase emissions is required. A review of pilot plant campaigns for AMP/PZ blends shows that CESAR1 performs better in terms of energy compared to MEA and degrades less. There is, however, the need for high-quality pilot campaigns where all data needed for process model validation is provided for the scientific community. Finally, amine emission mitigation strategies and data on the environmental impact and toxicity of AMP and PZ are presented and discussed.

1. Introduction

Global warming caused by anthropogenic CO₂ emissions constitutes a major and pressing societal issue. Measures are needed to stop anthropogenic emissions and slow down global warming. One of the most promising approaches to accomplish this is Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS). Chemical absorption is the most mature and cost-effective means of post-combustion CO₂-capture (Bui et al., 2018; Dutcher et al., 2015). Among the different kinds, amine-based solvents are the most used in CO₂ scrubbing technology, given their high absorption-kinetics rates, CO₂ absorption capacity and selectivity. The main drawback of this technology is the high energy demand to regenerate the solvent, Rochelle (2016). Furthermore, aqueous amine solvents can degrade under certain conditions, creating different operational issues such as higher corrosivity and foaming tendency, resulting in lower capture performances. Research on CO₂ capture by amine-based absorption is now focused on optimizing existing solvents, understanding possible

mitigation strategies, and designing stable and energy-saving systems. For CO₂-scrubbing technology, 30 wt% MEA (monoethanolamine) is still considered the benchmark solvent (Dai et al., 2012); Hosseini-Ardali et al. (2020). Feron et al. (2020) proposed CESAR1 as the new benchmark for absorption-based CO₂ capture technology. The CESAR1 solvent was developed in the FP7 project CESAR (2008 – 2011). It is an aqueous blend of 3 M AMP (2-amino-2-methyl-1-propanol) and 1.5 M PZ (piperazine), corresponding to an aqueous solution of approximately 27 wt% AMP and 13 wt% PZ (Brüder et al., 2011; Knudsen et al., 2011). The molecular structures of the primary sterically-hindered AMP and PZ, which is a diamine, are depicted in Fig. 1.

Being a sterically hindered amine, AMP has, in many ways, similar thermal properties to tertiary amines. Still, unlike tertiary amines, it can react with CO₂ to produce both carbamate (minor product) and bicarbonate/carbonate (major product) (Ciftja et al., 2011). On the other hand, PZ, as a bifunctional amine, can form three carbamate species: PZ carbamate, PZ dicarbamate and protonated PZ carbamate

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: hanna.knuutila@ntnu.no (H.K. Knuutila).

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of the amine components of CESAR1, piperazine (PZ), and 2-amino-2-methylpropanolamine (AMP).

(Ermatchkov et al., 2003). PZ, as a carbamate-forming amine, is characterized by fast kinetics, while AMP, as a sterically hindered primary amine, by high CO₂ equilibrium temperature sensitivity (Svendsen et al., 2011).

The reactions describing the AMP/PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system are given below:

The reaction set shows how chemically complex this system is, with 10 reactions and 15 different species involved.

Over the years, the CESAR1 solvent has captured attention as a promising solvent, outperforming MEA in terms of energy efficiency and degradation stability (Kvamsdal et al., 2016; Mangalapally and Hans Hasse, 2011; Moser et al., 2023; Tobiesen et al., 2017).

Further, CESAR1 has a high cyclic capacity and therefore a high ability to absorb CO₂ at absorber temperature and to desorb CO₂ at high temperature (Bernhardsen and Knuutila, 2017). The cyclic capacity is defined as the difference between the CO₂ concentration in the rich and lean solution. It can be easily estimated, disregarding the impact of absorption kinetics, using vapour-liquid equilibrium (VLE) data and operating temperatures of 40 °C and 120 °C, in the absorber and stripper, respectively, as well as 10 kPa and 20 kPa CO₂ pressure in entering flue gas and in the reboiler. It can be estimated to be almost twice in the case of CESAR1 ($2.01 \frac{\text{mol CO}_2}{\text{kg solution}}$) compared to that of 30 wt% MEA ($1.18 \frac{\text{mol CO}_2}{\text{kg solution}}$), (Aronu et al., 2011; Brüder et al., 2011). This has been confirmed in different pilot campaigns that will be discussed later in this review.

As mentioned above, the CESAR1 solvent has the great advantage of being more chemically stable than for example, MEA, meaning that it degrades slower under oxidising conditions and thermal stress encountered in the post-combustion capture process. Despite its high stability, degradation over time is inevitable, which will change the chemical composition of the CESAR1. To ensure smooth operation and that no hazardous products of degradation are emitted to the environment, it is important to have a thorough understanding of these degradation processes.

1.1. Process description

The CO₂-capture process by chemical absorption is based on the underlying capacity of the amine-based solvent to reversibly react with CO₂. A simplified schematic of the process is given in Fig. 2. The flue gas is cooled down in a direct contact cooler, DCC, to control both the temperature and the water content and fed into the bottom of the absorber column where it meets the solvent counter-currently over packed sections. The flue gas rises to the top while CO₂ is transferred to the liquid phase, where it reacts with the solvent. A water-wash section, which is a packed column, is common to prevent potential emissions of amine solvent and volatile degradation compounds by providing good contact between the gas phase and the wash water. Make-up water may be added to the water wash if required by the water balance. Further emission control units such as acid treatment and mist eliminators are also often considered to mitigate volatile amine and, when present, aerosol-based amine emissions, (Buvik et al., 2021). The CO₂-rich solvent is pumped from the bottom of the absorber to the top of the desorber unit, where it is regenerated by temperature swing with heat provided by the reboiler. Between the absorber and stripper columns, the solvent passes through a cross-heat exchanger, where the CO₂-rich stream is heated by the CO₂-lean stream. The outlet gas from the stripper is mostly CO₂ with some water and amines that are recovered by condensation. The product CO₂ can finally be compressed and sent to a transport unit for storage or utilization.

1.2. Aim and outline of the article

This review outlines the existing experimental gaps of the CESAR1 solvent to develop reliable thermodynamics, physical properties and kinetics models needed for process simulation and as a basis for CO₂ capture-plant design. Experimental thermodynamic, kinetics and physical properties for AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ aqueous solutions are reviewed together with modelling works for AMP/PZ blends. Further, pilot campaigns providing process performance data, data for validation of process models, solvent degradation data, and hands-on experience in operating the solvent are reviewed. Status on the knowledge of degradation of AMP/PZ blends and of the individual amines will be given, as well as an overview of the status on the knowledge related to amine and degradation compound emissions and environmental impacts of CESAR1. This work aims to outline the current experimental gaps rather than provide a performance-based comparison with other solvents for CO₂ capture.

The outline of this paper is arranged as follows:

1. Review of the available experimental thermodynamic data and models.
2. Review of the available experimental kinetics data and models.
3. Review of the available experimental physical properties data.
4. Review of degradation data for AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ aqueous solutions.
5. Review of the pilot campaigns using AMP/PZ blends and reported operational problems.
6. Review of the studies regarding emission and environmental impacts of CESAR1 solvent.

2. Thermodynamic properties, experimental data, modelling, and gaps

2.1. Vapour-liquid equilibrium (VLE) data

Design and simulation of industrial separation equipment for chemical absorption of CO₂ require adequate knowledge of chemical and phase equilibria. In rate-based CO₂ absorption models, which are needed to size the absorber column, vapour-liquid equilibrium with CO₂ defines the boundary conditions for the partial differential equations describing the mass transfer. Equilibrium measurements for AMP/H₂O,

Fig. 2. CO₂-capture by amine-based absorption, process schematization. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

PZ/H₂O and AMP/PZ/H₂O are necessary to understand the molecular interactions between the amines and water, to provide volatility and to estimate AMP and PZ emissions from the process and the water wash section. Furthermore, most activity-based thermodynamic models applied to CO₂ capture modelling require both CO₂-unloaded data and CO₂-loaded data (Borhani et al., 2021). At low acid gas concentrations, the phase equilibrium is governed by that of the binary or ternary if a blend of amines is used (alkanolamines/water system).

In this chapter, we present and discuss the vapour-liquid equilibrium data (VLE) for CO₂-unloaded and CO₂-loaded aqueous AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ solutions available in the open literature.

Table 1 shows the available volatility data for unloaded AMP/H₂O, PZ/H₂O, and AMP/PZ/H₂O systems. Volatility of AMP in CO₂-unloaded aqueous solutions data is available (Belabbaci et al., 2010; Hartono et al., 2013; Klepáčová et al., 2011; Pappa et al., 2006) covering temperatures up to 179 °C and up to pure AMP. The data shows that AMP is more volatile than MEA at the same concentration and temperature (Kim et al., 2008). This leads to higher gas phase amine contents, requiring careful water wash section design, other emission mitigation options, and process conditions to avoid high emissions compared to MEA.

Several studies report the volatility of PZ in CO₂-unloaded aqueous solutions (Hartono et al., 2013; Hilliard, 2008; Steele et al., 1997; VonNiederhausern et al., 2006), covering temperatures up to 380 °C for pure PZ and up to 100 °C for 40 wt% PZ aqueous solutions. Results show that PZ is less volatile than AMP and MEA at the same concentration and temperature but more volatile than MDEA, (Kim et al., 2008). PZ volatility data, in terms of y_{PZ} , are much more scattered than AMP data, most likely due to the very low volatility of PZ and the limited sensitivity of the analytical methods used, mostly titration, making the modelling work more challenging. Hartono et al. (2013) studied the volatility of AMP and PZ in a blend using a combination of titration

and ¹H NMR techniques to measure the amine concentration. Results showed that the change in PZ volatility is not significant when AMP concentration changes at a fixed PZ content and vice versa. Therefore, even though there is limited data for the blends of AMP/PZ, no further investigation on this is suggested for highly concentrated solutions. François et al. (2024) measured the volatility of CO₂-loaded and unloaded aqueous AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ solutions at water-wash relevant conditions providing highly needed data at low concentrations that can be used to fit models and design of water-wash sections. However, more AMP and PZ volatility data at low concentrations and various AMP/PZ ratios especially using degraded solutions could be beneficial for more realistic predictions of volatile emissions.

The collected VLE data for the AMP/H₂O/CO₂ system is available in Table 2. They cover a range in concentration from 0.54 wt% to 56 wt% of AMP and a range in temperature from 20 °C to 120 °C. François et al. (2024) measured CO₂ solubility data at low AMP concentration, 0.06 M (-0.54 wt%) and 0.3 M (-2.7 wt%). Hartono et al. (2020) also provided P_{CO_2} data at low AMP concentrations, 1 M (-9 wt%) and 0.1 M (-0.9 wt%). Murshid et al. (2011) measured VLE at 1 M (-9 wt%), but they did not cover a range of loadings of practical interest for the CO₂ capture operation. Many datasets are available for 30 wt% AMP, as this particular system has been employed as a reference to validate experimental equipment (Dash et al., 2011; Jane and Li, 1997; Kundu et al., 2003; Li and Chang, 1994; Seo and Hong, 1996; Teng and Mather, 1989; Tong et al., 2012). For 30 wt% AMP, the agreement among the data is generally good, however, at high loadings and lower temperatures, the measurements by Li and Chang (1994), Kundu et al. (2003) and Seo and Hong (1996) are not in agreement with each other, as shown in Fig. 3. Li and Chang (1994) and Seo and Hong (1996) data at 40 °C overlap data from Dash et al. (2011) and Teng and Mather (1989) at 50 °C. Tong et al. (2012) is the only one that measured CO₂ solubility at a typical stripping temperature, $T = 120$ °C,

Table 1
VLE data for CO₂ unloaded systems.

System	Experimental Range	Data Type	Instrument	Reference
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0.037 \div 0.30$ $T = 60 \div 100$ °C	y_{AMP}, P_{tot}	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	Hartono et al. (2013)
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 1$ $T = 74 \div 179$ °C	P_{tot}	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	Klepáčová et al. (2011)
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0 \div 1$ $T = 74 \div 179$ °C	P_{tot}	Static Pressure Device	Belabbaci et al. (2010)
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0 \div 1$ $P_{tot} = 66.7 \div 101.3$ kPa	T	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	Pappa et al. (2006)
AMP/H ₂ O	$m_{AMP} = 4.8$ m $T = 40 \div 65$ °C	P_{AMP}	Stirred Reactor with FTIR	Nguyen (2013)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.06, 0.5, 1 M $T = 40 \div 97$ °C	y_{AMP}, P_{tot}	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	François et al. (2024)
PZ/H ₂ O	$\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.05-0.65$ $x_{PZ} = 0.024 \div 0.11$ $T = 60 \div 100$ °C	y_{PZ}, P_{tot}	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	Hartono et al. (2013)
PZ/H ₂ O	$x_{PZ} = 1$ $T = 172 \div 382$ °C	P_{tot}	Flow method with ultralow residence times	VonNiederhausern et al. (2006)
PZ/H ₂ O	$x_{PZ} = 0.016-0.11$ $T = 32 \div 63$ °C	y_{PZ}, P_{tot}	Static VLE	Hilliard (2008)
PZ/H ₂ O	$x_{PZ} = 1$ $T = 145 \div 187$ °C	P_{tot}	Ebulliometer	Steele et al. (1997)
PZ/H ₂ O	$m_{PZ} = 8$ m $T = 50 \div 70$ °C	P_{PZ}	Stirred Reactor with FTIR	Nguyen (2013)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.15, 0.3 M $T = 40 \div 97$ °C	y_{PZ}, P_{tot}	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	François et al. (2024)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O	$\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.13-0.41$ $x_{AMP} = 0.012 \div 0.099$ $x_{PZ} = 0.010 \div 0.045$ $T = 60 \div 100$ °C	y_{AMP}, y_{PZ}, P_{tot}	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	Hartono et al. (2013)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O	$m_{AMP} = 2.3$ m $m_{PZ} = 5$ m $T = 50 \div 70$ °C	P_{AMP}, P_{PZ}	Stirred Reactor with FTIR	Nguyen (2013)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP + PZ] = 0.09, 0.9, 0.45 M [AMP]/[PZ] = 2 $T = 40 \div 97$ °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.05-0.65$	y_{AMP}, y_{PZ}, P_{tot}	Modified Swietoslowski Ebulliometer	François et al. (2024)

and data are reported as total pressure. At 100 °C and at low loadings, the Tong et al. (2012) and Li and Chang (1994) data are not in good agreement. This could be because, at low loadings, the partial pressure of CO₂ calculated from total pressure measurements, will have high uncertainty. In fact, Tong et al. (2012) measured the partial pressure of CO₂ by subtraction, while Li and Chang (1994) used online gas chromatography. The Seo and Hong (1996) and Li and Chang (1994) datasets are in excellent agreement with each other, while the Tong et al. (2012) P_{CO_2} measurements are slightly lower at high loadings. Hartono et al. (2020), Tontiwachwuthikul et al. (1991) and Roberts and Mather (1988) measured the CO₂ solubility in a 3 M AMP (~27 wt%) aqueous solution, which is the relevant concentration for the CESAR1 blend. These measurements show the same inconsistency as discussed above for 30 wt% AMP aqueous solutions. At high loading and low temperatures, the datasets are in bad agreement with each other, and the data are scattered.

Given the high absorption capacity of CESAR1 and the concentration of AMP in the CESAR1 solvent, it is important to have consistent data at high loadings, and more measurements at loadings higher than 0.6 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{AMP} should be performed.

The collected VLE data for the PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system are available in Table 3. PZ is often used as a promoter, as also in CESAR1; therefore, most of the data available is at low concentrations of PZ. However, Rochelle et al. (2011) proposed PZ as a new benchmark for CO₂ capture by chemical absorption, and data at higher concentrations are also available in the literature. The VLE data available in the open literature for the PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system cover a range of concentrations from 0.15 M (~1.3 wt%) to 4.9 M (~40 wt%) of PZ and a range of temperatures from 20 °C to 190 °C. (2021). François et al. (2024) measured CO₂ solubility in aqueous PZ solution at 0.3 M (~2.6 wt%) and 0.15 M (~1.3 wt%). Hartono et al. (2021) reported CO₂ solubility in aqueous

PZ solution at 1.5 M (~13 wt%), which is the relevant concentration for CESAR1, and data are available as P_{CO_2} up to 80 °C and as P_{tot} at 100 and 120 °C. These data are in good agreement with the ones reported by Ermatchkov et al. (2006) at a similar concentration, 1.7 M (~14 wt%). Dash et al. (2011) report CO₂ solubility in aqueous PZ solutions with concentrations ranging from 0.2 M (~1.7 wt%) to 4.5 M (~37 wt%). However, the measurements are limited up to 55 °C and therefore do not cover stripper operative conditions. Dugas and Rochelle (2011) report CO₂ solubility in aqueous PZ solution with PZ concentration going up to 5.8 M (~50 wt%), Bishnoi and Rochelle (2000) report CO₂ solubility in 0.6 M (~5 wt%) aqueous PZ solutions up to 70 °C. Their measurements are in excellent agreement with Derks et al. (2005) but show substantial discrepancies with the datasets by Aroua and Mohd Salleh (2004) and Bougie and Iliuta (2011). Xu and Rochelle (2011) measured CO₂ solubility in a highly concentrated PZ solution, 4.7 M (~40 wt%), up to 190 °C. Furthermore, high-pressure data at high loadings are available by Kamps et al. (2003), Kadiwala et al. (2010a), and Xu and Rochelle (2011). Overall, higher deviations between different datasets are detected for PZ compared to the AMP system.

In conclusion, aqueous PZ is a well-known system, and many data are available. However, more systematic experimental VLE studies would help to evaluate which data sets are more accurate. More data at lower concentrations of PZ would be helpful for water-wash section design, as these have to be as accurate as possible to minimize solvent emission.

Collected VLE data for the AMP/PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system are available in Table 4. The VLE data available in the open literature for the AMP/PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system covers a range of AMP concentrations going from 0.5 M up to 4 M and a range of PZ concentrations going from 0.5 M up to 4 M. Brüder et al. (2011), Yang et al. (2010) and Hartono et al. (2021) measured the CO₂ sol-

Table 2
CO₂ solubility data for AMP/H₂O/CO₂ system.

System	Experimental range	Data Type	Instrument	Reference
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.06–0.3 M T = 40 + 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.032 \pm 0.526$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	François et al. (2024)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2 M T = 40 + 60 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.74 \pm 1.04$	P_{TOT}	Equilibrium Cell	Kontos et al. (2022)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 3 M T = 40 + 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.07 \pm 0.96$	P_{TOT}	Reaction Calorimetry	Hartono et al. (2021)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.1, 1, 3 M T = 40 + 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0 \pm 1.95$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	Hartono et al. (2020)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$wf_{AMP} = 0.3$ T = 40 + 60 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.31$	P_{CO_2}, P_{AMP}	Stirred Reactor with FTIR	Nguyen (2013)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$wf_{AMP} = 0.3$ T = 40 + 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0 \pm 0.92$	P_{TOT}	Static-Analytic apparatus	Tong et al. (2012)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2.5, 3, 4, 9 M T = 25 + 55 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0 \pm 1.1$	P_{CO_2}	High Pressure Stainless Stirred Equilibrium Cell	Dash et al. (2011c)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 1, 2, 3 M T = 30 + 50 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 1 \pm 2.5$	P_{TOT}	High Pressure Solubility Cell	Murshid et al. (2011)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 3 M T = 40 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.385 \pm 0.939$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Equilibrium Cell	Yang et al. (2010)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2, 2.8, 3, 4 M T = 30 + 50 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.41 \pm 0.97$	P_{CO_2}	Stirred Glass Equilibrium Cell	Kundu et al. (2003)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2, 4 M T = 40 + 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.15 \pm 1.2$	P_{TOT}	Equilibrium Cell	Silkenbäumer et al. (1998)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2, 3, 4.3 M T = 30 + 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.11 \pm 0.99$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	Jane and Li (1997)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$wf_{AMP} = 0.3$ T = 40 + 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.28 \pm 0.90$	P_{CO_2}	Stirred Equilibrium Cell	Seo and Hong (1996)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$wf_{AMP} = 0.3$ T = 40 + 100 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.4 \pm 0.87$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	Li and Chang (1994)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2, 3 M T = 20 + 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.126 \pm 0.96$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	Tontiwachwuthikul et al. (1991)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2 M T = 40 + 50 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.126 \pm 0.96$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	Mather (1990)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 3.4 M T = 50 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.03 \pm 1.3$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	Teng and Mather (1989)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2, 3 M T = 40, 100 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.4 \pm 1.3$	P_{CO_2}	Equilibrium Jerguson Cell	Roberts and Mather (1988)

ubility at the CESAR1 concentration. The data comparison is shown in Fig. 4. The three datasets are in good agreement with each other at 40 °C and 60 °C, while at 80 °C, Yang et al. (2010) show lower partial pressures of CO₂ compared to the other work available. Hartono et al. (2021) and Bröder et al. (2011) measured CO₂ solubility at 100 °C and 120 °C, respectively, using reaction calorimetry and a high-temperature equilibrium apparatus. However, the data are not directly comparable since Hartono et al. (2021) provide total pressure data while Bröder et al. (2011) give CO₂ partial pressures. François et al. (2024) measured the CO₂ solubility in aqueous AMP/PZ solution at low amine concentrations (0.09 M, 0.45 M, 0.9 M) and at a fixed AMP/PZ molar ratio.

Datasets at different AMP/PZ ratios are available and can be used to develop a thermodynamic model for the absorption-stripper process. Even though François et al. (2024) provides some data at low amine concentrations, data at different AMP/PZ ratios to predict the aerosol

formation inside the column is still needed (Svendsen et al., 2021). Finally, for emission prediction measurements using degraded solutions are needed, as the complex matrix with numerous degradation compounds may impact the behaviour of the solvent. These constitute a gap in the existing literature.

2.2. Speciation data

Speciation data show the distribution of ionic and molecular species in the system and how their concentrations change with CO₂-loading. Good prediction of speciation in the system is important since the amount of each product is directly related to the absorption rate, impacting the kinetics of the CO₂ capture process and, therefore, the absorber height and the CAPEX of the process. Speciation will also impact the simulated heat of absorption/heat of desorption when rigorous thermodynamic models are used.

Fig. 3. CO₂ Solubility data in 30 wt% of AMP from different sources: ○ Kundu et al. (2003), □ Seo and Hong (1996), △ Li and Chang (1994), ▽ Teng and Mather (1989), ◇ Dash et al. (2011c). (Blue, 40 °C; Red, 50 °C). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

The available literature contains very little information about speciation for this system. Ciftja et al. (2014) used a technique that combines electroneutrality, mass balance for amine, pH measurement and NMR to measure full liquid speciation of aqueous 30 wt% AMP solution and showed that AMP-carbamate is formed in a much smaller amount than in other primary amine systems, such as MEA. Aqueous PZ solutions at different concentrations have been studied by Hilliard (2008), Ermatchkov et al. (2003) and Ciftja et al. (2014) at concentrations from 0.2 M (~1.7 wt%) to 3.6 M (~30 wt%). Li et al. (2014) studied the speciation of the AMP-PZ mixture and gathered a small number of data points to validate the thermodynamic model they developed. Therefore, given this small quantity of data, it is suggested to perform further speciation studies that can be used to build or validate rigorous thermodynamic and kinetic models for CESAR1 suitable for process simulations and process design.

2.3. Heat of absorption data

Information on the heat of reaction of CO₂ in aqueous amine solutions is of prime importance for evaluating the operative costs of the CO₂ capture because it is directly related to the steam requirements of the amine regeneration stage, constituting a significant fraction of the heat used in the stripper unit (Oexmann and Kather, 2010). It is also an integral part of a thermodynamic model. Hartono et al. (2021) and Kim (2009) employed reaction calorimetry

to measure the semi-differential heat of absorption in 26.8 wt% and 25 wt% AMP aqueous solutions, respectively. However, the data show different trends with temperature, and the averaged heat of absorption over the CO₂ loading (0.2–0.78 mol_{CO2}/mol_{amine}) shows deviations higher than 40 %. Arcis et al. (2007) measured integral heat of absorption in 15 wt% and 30 wt% AMP aqueous solutions using a flow calorimetric technique (Arcis et al., 2007). The heat of absorption of CO₂ data measured by Arcis et al. (2007) shows a weak dependency on the CO₂ loading, while Hartono et al. (2021) and Kim (2009) obtain a reduced heat of absorption of CO₂ with increased loading.

Hartono et al. (2021) measured the semi-differential heat of absorption of CO₂ in a 1.5 M (~13 wt%) PZ aqueous solutions while Kim (2009) in 1.7 M (~15 wt%) PZ aqueous solutions. Also, in this case, the data show different trends with temperature. At 40 °C, the heat of absorption averaged over the CO₂ loading range (0.068–0.94 mol_{CO2}/mol_{amine}) deviates less than 2 %, while at higher temperatures, deviation increases up to 45 %, however, the two sources show opposite temperature trends. Svensson et al. (2013) measured differential heat of absorption of CO₂ in a 19 wt% PZ solution by reaction calorimetry up to a loading of 0.2 mol_{CO2}/mol_{amine}. The heat of absorption of CO₂ averaged over the CO₂ loading had a deviation of 13 % compared to Kim (2009).

Regarding AMP/PZ blends, Hartono et al. (2021) reported the heat of absorption of CO₂ for different ratios of AMP and PZ (0.5/4, 1.5/3.0, 2.25/2.25, 3.0/1.5, 4.0/1.5, all units are M) as a function of CO₂ load-

Table 3
CO₂ solubility data for PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system.

System	Experimental range	Data type	Instrument	Reference
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.03–0.15 M T = 40 ÷ 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.109 \div 1.097$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	François et al. (2024)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 1.5 M T = 40 ÷ 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.24 \div 1.18$	P_{TOT}	Reaction Calorimetry	Hartono et al. (2021)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 2$ m T = 40 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 1.1 \div 1.6$	P_{TOT}	High Pressure Cell	Haghtalab et al. (2014)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 1.5 M T = 40 ÷ 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.24 \div 1.18$	P_{TOT} for $T \geq 100$ °C , P_{CO_2}	Atmospheric and High Pressure VLE apparatus	Hartono et al. (2021)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 8$ m T = 40 ÷ 65 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.3$	P_{CO_2} , P_{PZ}	Stirred Reactor with FTIR	Nguyen (2013)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 2, 5, 8, 12$ m T = 40 ÷ 100 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.44 \div 0.82$	P_{CO_2}	Wetted Wall Contactor	Dugas and Rochelle (2011)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 4, 9, 3-8$ m T = 100 ÷ 191 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.44 \div 0.82$	P_{CO_2} and P_{TOT}	Calorimeter and Autoclave	Xu and Rochelle (2011)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.2, 4.5 M T = 25 ÷ 55 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.24 \div 1.18$	P_{CO_2}	Equilibrium Cell	Dash et al. (2011)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 0.1, 0.5, 0.6, 3, 1$ m T = 20 ÷ 40 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.097 \div 1.47$	P_{CO_2} and P_{TOT}	Static Medium Pressure Apparatus	Bougie and Iliuta (2011)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.3, 1.2 M T = 40 ÷ 70 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.92 \div 2.77$	P_{TOT}	High-Pressure Jerguson Cell	Kadiwala et al. (2010b)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 0.89-5$ m T = 40 ÷ 60 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.22 \div 0.89$	P_{CO_2} , P_{PZ} , P_{H_2O}	Stirred Reactor with FTIR	Hilliard (2008)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 1, 2, 4$ m T = 20 ÷ 40 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.097 \div 1.47$	P_{CO_2}	Headspace Gas Chromatography	Ermatchkov et al. (2006)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.6 M T = 25 ÷ 70 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.36 \div 1.08$	P_{CO_2}	Continuous Stirred Cell Apparatus	Derks et al. (2005)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 1 M T = 25 ÷ 50 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.098 \div 1.23$	P_{CO_2}	Double-Jacketed Stirred Cell Reactor	Aroua and Mohd Salleh (2004)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	$m_{PZ} = 2, 4$ m T = 40 ÷ 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0 \div 1.68$	P_{TOT}	Thermostated High Pressure Cell	Kamps et al. (2003)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.6 M T = 40 ÷ 70 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.16 \div 0.96$	P_{CO_2}	Wetted Wall Contactor	Bishnoi and Rochelle (2000)

ing and temperature. Xie et al. (2013) measured the heat of absorption of CO₂ with aqueous 3.0/0.5, 4.0/1.0 and 3.0/1.5 M AMP/PZ aqueous solution at 40, 60 and 80 °C. At 40 °C the heat of absorption data from Hartono et al. (2021) and Xie et al. (2013) averaged over the CO₂ loading range (0.3–0.8 mol_{CO2}/mol_{amine}) shows a 20 % relative deviation, while at 60 °C averaged over CO₂ loadings (0.2–0.8 mol_{CO2}/mol_{amine}) the relative deviation is 8.6 %, and at 80 °C averaged over CO₂ loadings (0.2–0.6 mol_{CO2}/mol_{amine}) the relative deviation is 10 %.

Additional research on the heat of absorption of CO₂ for AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ systems would be helpful in developing rigorous thermodynamic models and predicting the energy consumption.

2.4. Solid liquid equilibrium (SLE) data

The formation of slurries and solids in an absorption plant may create unforeseen process conditions, decrease equipment efficiency, and create clogging, which will result in hazardous operations. CESAR1 is a solvent with a relatively high concentration of piperazine. It is a solid at high concentration and the solubility limit may be reached. Such conditions may occur especially during plant stops when the liquid temperature drops and at high CO₂ loadings.

Fosbøl et al. (2011) reported freezing point depression (FPD) data for the AMP-H₂O system up to 44 wt% AMP concentration. Neerup et al. (2019) improved the above-mentioned work measuring FPD data for AMP-H₂O systems up to pure AMP, revealing the existence of a tetrahydrate phase by Powder X-ray diffraction. However, solid-liquid equilibrium data for CO₂-loaded AMP aqueous solutions are not available in the open literature.

Bishnoi and Rochelle (2002) and Muhammad et al. (2009) reported the solid solubility of PZ in water from 20 °C up to 70 °C. These measurements are in good agreement with each other. Freeman et al. (2009) reported the solid-liquid transition temperature for aqueous PZ solutions over a range of concentrations between 8 wt% up to 73 wt%. Freeman et al. (2009) also measured PZ solid solubility of CO₂-loaded solutions of 40.2 wt% and 45.4 wt% PZ concentrations and with operative loadings up to ~0.65 mol_{CO2}/mol_{PZ}. The Dow Chemical Company also reported data for the solubility of PZ. Data comparison with Bishnoi's and Freeman's results is available in Freeman et al. (2009). Hilliard (2008) measured the solid solubility of PZ by differential scanning calorimetry for piperazine concentrations up to 77 wt%. The results are, however, not in agreement with the ones mentioned above. Fosbøl et al. (2011) reported FPD data for PZ-H₂O up to 90 wt% PZ con-

Table 4
CO₂ solubility data for AMP/PZ/H₂O/CO₂ system.

System	Experimental range	Data type	Instrument	Reference
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP+PZ] = 0.09, 0.45, 0.9 M [AMP/PZ] = 2 T = 40 ÷ 80 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.045 \div 0.97$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	François et al. (2024)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP/PZ] = 3.0/1.5, 4.0/0.5, 0.5/4.0, 1.5/3.0, 2.25/2.25 T = 40 ÷ 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.035 \div 1.05$	P_{TOT} for $T \geq 100$ °C P_{CO_2}	Reaction Calorimetry	Hartono et al. (2021)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[wt _{AMP} /wt _{PZ}] = 25/5, 20/10 % T = 40 ÷ 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0 \div 0.95$	P_{TOT}	Static Analytical Apparatus	Tong et al. (2013)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[m _{AMP} /m _{PZ}] = 2.3/5, 4/2 m T = 20 ÷ 160 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.268 \div 0.65$	P_{CO_2}	Wetted Wall Column	Li et al. (2013)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[wt _{AMP} /wt _{PZ}] = 38/2, 35/5, 32/8, 45/5, 42/8 % T = 30 ÷ 55 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.22 \div 1.03$	P_{CO_2}	Equilibrium Cell	Dash et al. (2012)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP/PZ] = 3.0/1.5 T = 40 ÷ 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.04 \div 0.83$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique and High Pressure VLE	Brüder et al. (2011)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP/PZ] = 3.0/1.5 T = 40 ÷ 120 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.04 \div 0.83$	P_{CO_2}	Vapor Recirculation Technique	Yang et al. (2010)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	m _{AMP} = 2.3 m m _{PZ} = 5 m T = 50 ÷ 70 °C $\alpha_{CO_2} = 0.3$	$P_{CO_2}, P_{AMP}, P_{PZ}$	Stirred Reactor with FTIR	Nguyen (2013)

Fig. 4. CO₂ solubility data for CESAR1 system: □ Brüder et al. (2011), ○ Hartono et al. (2021), ◇ Yang et al. (2010) (Blue, 40 °C; Green, 60 °C; Orange, 80 °C). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

Table 5
Available thermal properties data for AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ aqueous solutions.

System	Experimental range	Data Type	Instrument	Reference
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0.062-1$ $T = 5 \div 95$ °C	C_p	Differential Scanning Calorimeter	Zhang et al. (2002)
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0.2-1$ $T = 30 \div 80$ °C	C_p	Differential Scanning Calorimeter	Chen and Li (2001)
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0.2-1$ $T = 30 \div 80$ °C	C_p	Differential Scanning Calorimeter	Chiu and Li (1999)
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0.05-0.90$ $T = 25,35$ °C	H_{Excess}	Heat-flow calorimeter, Setaram C-80	Mathonat et al. (1997)
AMP/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 1$ $T = 20 \div 140$ °C	k	Thermal Conductivity Cell	Zhang and Xu (2001)
PZ/H ₂ O	$x_{PZ} = 0.05-1$ $T = 30 \div 140$ °C	C_p	Differential Scanning Calorimeter	Chen et al. (2010b)
PZ/H ₂ O	$x_{PZ} = 1$ $T = 30 \div 140$ °C	C_p	Differential Scanning Calorimeter	Steele et al. (1997)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O	$x_{AMP} = 0.04 \div 0.32$ $x_{PZ} = 0.02-0.24$ $T = 30 \div 80$ °C	C_p	Differential Scanning Calorimeter	Chen et al. (2010a)

centration using a modified Beckmann apparatus. Kim et al. (2012) studied the solid-liquid solubility and crystal morphology, including formation and dissolution, in CO₂-loaded and unloaded aqueous PZ solution by focused beam reflectance measurements and particle vision measurements.

Solid-liquid equilibrium data for the AMP/PZ blend exist (Fosbøl et al., 2011; Neerup et al., 2019). It is found that the freezing point of the solutions decreases with the addition of AMP. Li et al. (2013) studied the transition temperature for selected solutions of PZ/AMP up to a loading of 0.3 mol_{CO2}/mol_{alkalinity}.

However, as no data is available for the CO₂ loaded blend of AMP/PZ at the CESAR1 concentration, further investigations are necessary to ensure design and operation without issues regarding precipitation since the effect of CO₂ loading may contribute to the formation of solids in the system.

In conclusion, solid-liquid equilibrium data are available for CO₂ unloaded systems. Experimental gaps for solid liquid equilibrium data for aqueous AMP solution and for AMP/PZ aqueous solutions have been detected, and further work is suggested to ensure industrial operation without precipitation.

2.5. Thermal property data: liquid heat capacity, excess enthalpy, thermal conductivity

Thermal property data such as heat capacity and thermal conductivity are required for the design of the heat exchanger equipment used in gas-treating processes. Furthermore, excess enthalpy data and liquid heat capacity data, when available, have been effectively used in fitting VLE models, Hartono et al. (2020), Zhang and Chen (2011), Zhang et al. (2011). A review of the following properties for AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ is given, and data are available in Table 5.

Regarding the AMP system, the liquid heat-capacity measurements by different sources are in good agreement at low temperatures, while at higher temperatures the Zhang et al. (2002) measurements are lower than those of Chiu and Li (1999) and Chen et al. (2010a). Regarding the PZ system, the two sources available cover only heat capacity. They are in good agreement, as also reported by Chen et al., who used Steele's measurements as validation for their method (Chen et al., 2010b) and (Steele et al., 1997). Regarding the aqueous AMP/PZ blends, only one dataset for liquid heat-capacity data is available (Chen et al., 2010a). However, it covers a large range of concentrations, including the CESAR1 concentration.

Further research on measurements of CO₂-loaded AMP/PZ aqueous solutions is suggested. Only one experimental study on the thermal conductivity of the CESAR1 subsystems has been found in the open literature, and it uses pure AMP solutions, (Zhang and Xu, 2001). However,

Table 6
Selected VLE models for AMP/PZ blends.

Reference	Model	Software
Yang et al. (2010)	Kent-Eisenberg	In-house code
Brüder et al. (2011)	Soft polynomial model	In-house code
Dash et al. (2012)	e-NRTL	Aspen Plus
Tong et al. (2013)	Kent-Eisenberg	In-house code
Li et al. (2014)	e-NRTL	Aspen Plus
Sherman (2016)	e-NRTL	Aspen Plus
Hartono et al. (2021)	e-NRTL	In-house code
Yi et al. (2024)	e-NRTL	Aspen Plus

a good estimation of the thermal conductivity is necessary for a proper design and correct cost estimation of the heat exchangers in the process.

2.6. Review of the thermodynamic models for AMP/PZ blends

The primary objective of thermodynamic modelling for aqueous amine solutions is to study speciation, predict CO₂-solubility as a function of solvent composition, temperature, and pressure, and determine the heat of absorption. In addition, a reliable kinetic model that takes into account the system reversibility requires a consistent and validated thermodynamic model. Selected VLE models and correlations for AMP/PZ blends are available in Table 6.

Dash et al. (2012) developed an e-NRTL model in the Aspen Plus environment for AMP/PZ blends. The model was regressed based on the solubility data from Yang et al. (2010) and their own work, Dash et al. (2012). The model was tested at the CESAR1 concentration against the Brüder et al. (2011) measurements and found to be in good agreement. However, the model developed by Dash et al. (2012) has been fitted on different datasets and found to be inconsistent with data published later. Therefore, a revision of the model is thought to be necessary and further improvements are suggested. Sherman (2016) developed an e-NRTL model in the Aspen Plus environment for AMP/PZ blends. The model performance is discussed only for a single concentration, 4 m AMP/ 2 m PZ (~ 23 wt% AMP/ 11 wt% PZ), as that is the concentration of the mass transfer data fitted to the hydraulics model developed. The work by Sherman (2016) provides interesting insights and discussions on the speciation and heat absorption predictions for aqueous AMP/PZ. However, the models were not fitted on data at CESAR1 concentration and improvements are needed once experimental gaps are filled. Li et al. (2014) also developed a model for AMP/PZ blends in the Aspen Plus environment. The model developed predicts the CO₂ solubility data reasonably well, the heat of absorption trend and the speciation based on the available data. Brüder et al. (2011), in their screening work to find the optimal AMP/PZ ratio with the highest cyclic

capacity, collected data for the CESAR1 concentration and developed a polynomial soft model. The correlation proposed has the advantage of being easy to implement and has been used to simulate the absorption process in simulation tools such as CO2SIM, Kvamsdal et al. (2011). However, this simple approach is limited since it does not provide an indication of the speciation, and it is not flexible to possible concentration changes in the plant due to amine degradation, emission, or precipitation. Yang et al. (2010) and Tong et al. (2013) developed a Kent-Eisenberg model to correlate their experimental results. Tong's model was fitted on their own data at 20/10 and 25/15 AMP/PZ wt% and it does not cover the CESAR1 concentration. On the other hand, the Yang model included data for the CESAR1 concentration. However, the model is limited to 80 °C and it is believed to be inaccurate at higher temperatures since CO₂ solubility data do not agree at high temperatures with those of Brüder et al. (2011) and Hartono et al. (2021) as shown in Fig. 4. While the Kent-Eisenberg model is easy to implement and has been found to be accurate in predicting CO₂-solubility, addressing the non-ideality only on the equilibrium constant may create inconsistencies for other thermodynamic properties such as speciation, amine volatility, and heat of absorption. Hartono et al. (2021) developed an e-NRTL model for AMP/PZ blends. The model covers the CESAR1 concentration and can accurately predict the CO₂-solubility and the heat of absorption. Yi et al. (2024) developed an open-access e-NRTL-based thermodynamic framework for aqueous AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ solutions in Aspen Plus. The model developed covers the CESAR1 concentration and can accurately predict the CO₂ solubility and the heat of absorption.

3. Kinetic properties, experimental data, modelling and gaps

3.1. Absorption kinetics data

CO₂ absorption operation using aqueous amines is a reactive process, and an accurate prediction of the reaction kinetics is essential for the design, simulation, and operation of any CO₂ capture process.

Data for CO₂ absorption kinetics using AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ aqueous solutions is available in the open literature and is collected and reviewed in this work, see Table 7. Experimental data are reported either as: k_{obs} , first order kinetics constant, k_2 second order kinetics constant, N_{CO_2} , experimental flux of CO₂ or k_L , experimental liquid side mass transfer coefficient. These properties are correlated to each other through Eq (11), where LMPD is the logarithmic mean pressure difference, k_g is the gas-phase mass transfer film coefficient, D_{CO_2} is the diffusion coefficient of CO₂, H_{CO_2} is the Henry's Constant of CO₂ and [amine] is the amine concentration.

$$N_{CO_2} = \frac{LMPD}{\frac{1}{k_g} + \frac{1}{k_L}} = \frac{LMPD}{\frac{1}{k_g} + \frac{H_{CO_2}}{\sqrt{k_{obs} \cdot D_{CO_2}}}} = \frac{LMPD}{\frac{1}{k_g} + \frac{H_{CO_2}}{\sqrt{k_2 \cdot [amine] \cdot D_{CO_2}}}} \quad (11)$$

In general, the AMP solvent has a large absorption capacity but slow absorption kinetics compared to other primary amines, such as MEA. Xu et al. (1996) measured the absorption rate constant k_2 for AMP at 25 °C to be 708 $\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}}$, while Luo et al. (2012) measured the absorption rate constant k_2 for MEA in a concentration range from 0.5 to 5 M, and found it to be 8256 $\frac{\text{kmol}}{\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{s}}$, and therefore more than ten times higher than AMP. Therefore, in the CESAR1 solvent, PZ is added as a promoter. Sun et al. (2005) measured the kinetics constant in AMP/PZ solutions at a fixed AMP concentration of 1 M and 1.5 M and changing PZ concentrations from 0.1 to 0.4 M. They found that an increase of 0.1 M of PZ resulted in a k_{obs} , which is twice as high. The enhancing effect of the AMP and PZ blend system is mutual. A higher PZ concentration results in a higher kinetics-promoting effect, while a higher AMP concentration implies a preference for accepting protons, leading to increased free PZ concentration and stronger kinetic effects (Khan et al., 2019b; Puxty and Rowland, 2011; Sun et al., 2005).

Regarding aqueous AMP solutions, CO₂-absorption kinetics data are widely available in the open literature. Chakraborty et al. (1986) were

among the first to study AMP, using a stirred cell. They concluded that the reaction took place in the fast reaction regime and that the effect of AMP on bicarbonate formation was much stronger than the direct reaction with OH⁻. Sodiq et al. (2014), Ali (2005) and Alper (1990) used a stopped-flow apparatus, while Dash et al. (2011), Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2009), Chen (2011), Seo and Hong (2000), Saha et al. (1995) and Yih and Shen (1988) used a wetted wall contactor. Choi et al. (2007), Messaoudi and Sada (1996), Xu et al. (1996), Camacho et al. (2005) and Bosch et al. (1990) used a stirred cell reactor to measure CO₂-absorption kinetics into aqueous AMP solutions. The Seo and Hong (2000) measurements give lower k_{obs} at 30 °C compared to the Ali (2005) and Sodiq et al. (2014) data, while the Seo and Hong measurements at 30 °C overlap Xu et al. (1996) measurements at 25 °C. Bosch et al. (1990) reported an estimated inaccuracy of 100 % for their calculation of k_2 . In fact, the Bosch data show a significant discrepancy with other reported measurements. However, most of the datasets are in good agreement with each other.

Regarding aqueous PZ solutions, a higher scatter in the kinetics measurements is found compared to aqueous AMP. Ullah et al. (2019) used a pressure drop method, Ume et al. (2013) and Rayer et al. (2011) a stopped-flow technique, while Li et al. (2013), Dugas (2009), Bishnoi and Rochelle (2000) and Sun et al. (2005) used a wetted wall column, and Derks et al. (2006) and Bindwal et al. (2011) used a stirred cell reactor to measure CO₂-absorption kinetics into aqueous PZ solutions. Bishnoi and Rochelle (2000) reported the rate of absorption for 0.2 M and 0.6 M PZ concentrations for CO₂ unloaded solutions up to 60 °C and for CO₂-loaded solutions up to 0.3 M and at different operative CO₂ loadings up to 0.67 mol_{CO2}/mol_{PZ}. Sun et al. (2005) measured the kinetics starting from CO₂-unloaded solutions up to 1 M PZ and 40 °C; the determined $k_{2,PZ}$ is smaller than the one measured by Bishnoi and Rochelle (2000). The measurements of Sun et al. (2005) at 40 °C overlap with Derks et al. (2006) at 25 °C. Dugas (2009) and Li (2015) measured the absorption kinetics of CO₂ aqueous solutions in a range of concentration from 2 m to 12 m and temperature from 20 °C to 100 °C.

Regarding AMP/PZ blends, Sodiq et al. (2014) used a stopped-flow apparatus, while Khan et al. (2019a), Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2009), Li (2015), Sun et al. (2005) and Seo and Hong (2000) used a wetted wall contactor for the kinetics measurements. The activation energies for $k_{2,PZ}$ and $k_{2,AMP}$ measured by Khan et al. (2019b) are in excellent agreement with the activation energies for PZ and AMP estimated respectively by Bishnoi and Rochelle (2000) and Saha et al. (1995) on the single subsystems, giving consistency and reliability to the measurements run for the blends. Kinetics measurements from different groups using various equipment are more difficult to evaluate and review since they depend on the chemical framework chosen to interpret the data.

Table 7 shows an important temperature limitation in the existing literature data since the highest temperature for most studies is 40 °C. It is known that operative conditions in the absorber, where the kinetics plays a crucial role, typically reach temperatures much higher than 40 °C. The reaction rate and reversibility of CO₂-absorption reactions increase with temperature, and data interpretation will be more complicated, but kinetics models built on data at higher temperatures would be more reliable for process model development. There is also a limitation on the amine concentration of the aqueous solutions used in the literature. For the AMP subsystem, kinetics data are available from 0.01 to 3.5 M, and for the PZ subsystem from 0.01 to 6.2 M, covering the CESAR1 concentration. However, AMP/PZ blend data are available for a broad range of concentrations of AMP and PZ but not at the CESAR1 concentration. Thus, kinetics measurements with the CESAR1 concentration should be performed.

Furthermore, kinetics experiments are often performed starting from CO₂-unloaded solutions, as also seen in Table 7, to limit the influence of reversible reactions and produce data that are easier to interpret. The main products of the reaction of aqueous solutions of AMP with CO₂ are found to be bicarbonate (HCO₃⁻), protonated AMP (AMPH⁺), and AMP carbamate (AMPCOO⁻). However, the underlying mechanism of

Table 7
CO₂ absorption kinetics data for AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ aqueous solutions.

System	Experimental range	Data Type	Instrument	Reference
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.05÷0.35 M T = 25 + 40 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α < 0.06	k _{obs} and k ₂	Stopped Flow Technique	Sodiq et al. (2014)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 3.3 M T = 40 °C P _{CO₂} = 5, 7, 14 kPa α = 0.15 – 0.6	N _{CO₂} and k _L	Wetted Wall Contactor	Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2009)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	m _{AMP} = 4.8 m T = 40–100 °C P _{CO₂} = 0 – 80 kPa α = NR	k _L	Wetted Wall Column	Chen (2011)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.23 ÷ 0.92 M T = 30,40 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α = NR	k _{obs}	Stopped Flow Technique	Ali (2005)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.12 ÷ 2.9 M T = 15 - 40 °C P _{CO₂} = Pure α = NR	N _{CO₂} and k ₂	Stirred tank	Camacho et al. (2005)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.5 ÷ 3.55 M T = 30,40 °C P _{CO₂} = 3.2 ÷ 7.7 kPa α = NR	k _{obs}	Wetter Sphere Contactor	Seo and Hong (2000)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.5 ÷ 2 M T = 20,30,40 °C P _{CO₂} = 0.15 ÷ 11 kPa α = NR	k ₂	Stirred Cell Reactor	Messaoudi and Sada (1996)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.24 ÷ 3.5 M T = 15 + 45 °C P _{CO₂} = 3.2 ÷ 7.7 kPa α = NR	k _{obs}	Stirred Cell Reactor	Xu et al. (1996)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.5 ÷ 2 M T = 21 + 45 °C P _{CO₂} = 5 ÷ 15 kPa α = NR	k ₂	Wetted Wall Contactor	Saha et al. (1995)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.013 ÷ 1.5 M T = 5 + 25 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α = NR	k _{obs} and k ₂	Stopped-Flow technique	Alper (1990)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = NR T = 42 °C P _{CO₂} = Pure NR α = NR	k ₂	Stirred cell	Chakraborty et al. (1986)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.2 ÷ 2.4 M T = 25 °C P _{CO₂} = 0.1 kPa α = NR	k ₂	Stirred Cell Reactor	Bosch et al. (1990)
AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.26 ÷ 3 M T = 40 °C P _{CO₂} = 0.1 kPa α = NR	k ₂	Wetted Wall Contactor	Yih and Shen (1988)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.05 ÷ 0.3 M T = 25 + 30 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α = NR	k _{obs}	Pressure Drop Method	Ullah et al. (2019)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	m _{PZ} = 8 m T = 20 -100 °C P _{CO₂} = 0 – 87.7 kPa α = 0.614 – 0.844	k _L	Wetted Wall Column	Li (2015)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.01 ÷ 0.05 M T = 5 ÷ 25 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α < 0.05	k _{obs}	Stopped-Flow Apparatus	Ume et al. (2013)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.025 ÷ 0.1 M T = 30 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α < 0.05	k ₂	Stirred-Cell Reactor	Bindwal et al. (2011)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.02 ÷ 0.1 M T = 30 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α < 0.001	k _{obs}	Stopped-Flow Apparatus	Rayer et al. (2011)

(continued on next page)

Table 7 (continued)

System	Experimental range	Data Type	Instrument	Reference
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	m _{PZ} = 2–12 m T = 40–100 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α = 0.462 – 1	k _L	Wetted Wall Column	Dugas (2009)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.2 - 0.8 M T = 25 - 40 °C P _{CO₂} = 1 - 4.92 kPa	k ₂	Wetted Wall Column	Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2007)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.06 ÷ 1.5 M T = 20 ÷ 40 °C P _{CO₂} = 0.25 ÷ 47.2 kPa α < 0.025	k ₂	Stirred-Cell Reactor	Derks et al. (2006)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.23 ÷ 0.92 M T = 30 ÷ 40 °C P _{CO₂} = 3.2 ÷ 7.7 kPa α _{max} = 0.74	k _{obs}	Wetted Wall Column	Sun et al. (2005)
PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[PZ] = 0.2, 0.6 M T = 23 ÷ 61 °C P _{CO₂} = 7 ÷ 195 kPa α < 0.01	k ₂	Wetted Wall Column	Bishnoi and Rochelle (2000)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2.25 ÷ 3.12 M [PZ] = 0.05 ÷ 0.3 M T = 25 ÷ 30 °C P _{CO₂} = 5, 15 kPa α < 0.1	N _{CO₂}	Wetted Wall Column	Khan et al. (2019a)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	m _{AMP} = 2.3/4 m m _{PZ} = 5/2 m T = 20 -100 °C P _{CO₂} = 0.05 - 229 kPa α = 0.41 - 0.78	k _L	Wetted Wall Column	Li et al. (2013)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.006 ÷ 0.024 M [PZ] = 0.007 ÷ 0.048 M T = 25 ÷ 40 °C	k _{obs}	Stopped Flow Technique	Sodiq et al. (2014)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 3.57 - 4.43 M [PZ] = 0 - 0.92 M T = 30 ÷ 50 °C P _{CO₂} = 5 - 15 kPa α = 0.25 - 0.9	N _{CO₂}	Wetted Wall Contactor	Dash et al. (2011)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 2.49 ÷ 3.14 M [PZ] = 0.23 ÷ 0.94 M T = 25 ÷ 40 °C P _{CO₂} = NR α = NR	N _{CO₂}	Wetted Wall Contactor	Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2009)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 3.4 M [PZ] = 0.12 ÷ 0.59 M T = 30 ÷ 70 °C P _{CO₂} = Pure(moist) α = NR	N _{CO₂}	Agitated vessel	Choi et al. (2007)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 1, 1.5 M [PZ] = 0.1 ÷ 0.4 M T = 30 ÷ 40 °C P _{CO₂} = 2.63 ÷ 4.55 kPa α < 0.1	k _{obs}	Wetted Wall Column	Sun et al. (2005)
AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	[AMP] = 0.55 ÷ 3.35 M [PZ] = 0.058, 0.115 0.233 M T = 30, 40 °C P _{CO₂} = 2.63 ÷ 4.55 kPa α = NR	k ₂	Wetted-Sphere absorption apparatus	Seo and Hong (2000)

CO₂ capture for a sterically hindered amine such as AMP is still not fully understood. Carbamate is present at a concentration one order of magnitude lower than bicarbonate and carbonate (Ciftja et al., 2014). Different studies assess that the carbamate formed is highly unstable due to the steric hindrance and gets hydrolysed to bicarbonate, Eq (12), (Sartori and Savage, 1983),

This instability of AMP carbamate leads to an easy breakdown to release CO₂ and amine in the stripping process, resulting in a higher CO₂ loading and a lower desorption heat requirement than conventional primary amines. Also, Sherman (2016) discusses the role of AMP-carbamate on the CO₂ absorption kinetics. As the plant will be operated with CO₂-loaded conditions, kinetics data measured starting from

unloaded solutions may not correctly represent the kinetics in the absorber. The reason could be that the initial formation of AMP carbamate is expected to be rapid compared to high-loading conditions where no carbamate is formed as slow bicarbonate formation takes over. Therefore, CO₂-loaded kinetics measurements for AMP and AMP/PZ blends at relevant operative conditions are considered an experimental gap in this review since they could provide a better kinetics framework for process simulations. The CO₂-loaded kinetics are also needed to describe the potential growth of any aerosol particles (Svendsen et al., 2021).

3.2. Review of the kinetics models for AMP/PZ blends

The kinetics modelling works for aqueous AMP/PZ blends have been summarized in Table 8.

Table 8
CO₂ absorption kinetics models for AMP/PZ aqueous solutions.

Reference	Model	Correlation
Hartono et al., 2021c	Termolecular Mechanism using concentration	*
Khan et al. (2019a)	AMP: Second-order PZ: Second-order	$\ln(k_{2,AMP}) = 32.52 - \frac{6433.73}{T}$ $\ln(k_{2,PZ}) = 23.69 - \frac{5172.2}{T}$
Sun et al. (2005)	AMP: Zwitterion PZ: Second-order	$\ln(k_{2,PZ}) = 29.13 - \frac{5712}{T}$ $\ln(k_{2,AMP}) = 17.29 - \frac{3034}{T}$
Sherman (2016)	Termolecular Mechanism using equilibrium activities	*
Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2009)	Penetration model	*

* The kinetics model is omitted in consideration of space constraints and to enhance readability.

Hartono et al. (2021c) developed a concentration-based termolecular model for AMP/PZ aqueous blends. The developed model predicts the apparent kinetic rate constant within 15.6 % on the fitted dataset. Khan et al. (2019a) consider the reaction between AMP and CO₂ to be a second-order reaction, while PZ solution can be represented with a zwitterion mechanism, where the zwitterion formation is the controlling step, leading to a second-order reaction of CO₂ for PZ as well. The developed model is valid up to 40 °C and for 28/2, 25/5, 22/8 and 20/10 AMP/PZ wt%. Sun et al. (2005) used a hybrid kinetic model. A second-order reaction for CO₂ and a zwitterion mechanism for CO₂ with AMP were used to interpret the results, considering PZ as a possible deprotonating base, and were found to predict their data within 7.7 % deviation. The model is valid up to 40 °C and at a fixed concentration of AMP of 1.0 M (~9 wt%) and 1.5 M (~13 wt%) and PZ concentration going from 0.1 M (~0.8 wt%) to 0.4 M (~3.4 wt%). The AMP kinetics constant was obtained from the kinetics data of the blend. It has been calculated that the reaction rate of the deprotonation step predicted by Sun et al. (2005) is 200 times higher than the formation of the zwitterion showing that a termolecular mechanism could have been successfully used for AMP to correlate their data. Sherman (2016) in his PhD thesis, investigated the absorption kinetics of AMP/PZ using a termolecular mechanism, mole fraction-based and activity-based. The model was fitted to the experimental data by Li (2015). The fit of the CO₂ flux data is poor and the errors are large. However, no systematic trend in the errors is detected. Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2009) developed a combined mass-transfer kinetics-equilibrium model, according to Higbie's penetration theory. The chemical framework developed considers a direct reaction of AMP with CO₂ to form bicarbonate, neglecting, therefore, the formation of AMP-carbamate. The reaction rate constant for the reaction of AMP with CO₂ has been determined by Saha et al. (1995). In the case of PZ, the formation of a zwitterion is the rate-limiting step, while the deprotonation step is at equilibrium since it considers only proton transfer reactions. The model fitted the reaction rate constant of PZ-carbamate and PZ-dicarbamate from zwitterion deprotonation by AMP as a base. The developed model is valid up to 40 °C and CO₂-partial pressures up to 14 kPa.

The kinetics modelling gaps are closely linked to the experimental gaps detected and discussed above, especially related to the AMP reaction mechanism with CO₂. Thus, further research on the kinetics model for AMP/PZ blends, validated on missing CESAR1 data, is therefore suggested.

4. Physical properties, experimental data and gaps

4.1. Physical properties: density, viscosity, CO₂ physical solubility, diffusivity, and surface tension

The chemical absorption of CO₂ takes place in a contactor, commonly a packed column, where both the CO₂ concentration and the temperature change. This results in changes in the physical properties, such as density, viscosity, and surface tension, through the contactor. This has an impact on the overall mass transfer coefficient and, thus, the mass transfer between gas and liquid along the absorber column.

Karunarathne et al. (2017) studied the effect of the uncertainty in physical properties, such as density, viscosity, and surface tension, on the mass transfer coefficients and interfacial area of structured and random packings for CO₂ capture using 30 wt% MEA. They found that viscosity has a larger effect than density and surface tension on the mass transfer coefficient, k_L , since a 5 % uncertainty in viscosity results in around 4 % uncertainty of the k_L . Viscosity affects the mass transfer coefficient through the turbulence in the liquid phase and the diffusion coefficient of various species. Surface tension impacts the wetting of the packing and, therefore, the mass transfer area. Surface tension has a higher impact on the interfacial area than viscosity and density since a 5 % uncertainty in surface tension results in around 3.5 % uncertainty of the interfacial area. Density does not significantly affect the design of the absorber and stripper unit (Karunarathne et al., 2017). However, accurate density models for CO₂-loaded solutions can be important during operation because density measurements can be adopted as online measurements correlated to the CO₂ loading in the lean and rich amine stream.

Tables with literature references for physical properties data for aqueous AMP, PZ and AMP/PZ solutions are available in the Supplementary Materials together with a separate reference list.

Density measurements are published in the open literature for aqueous AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ solutions. Data on aqueous AMP solutions is provided for the whole range of concentrations and temperatures up to 90 °C. There is just one CO₂-loaded dataset at 30 wt% of AMP (Stec et al., 2016). Density measurements for aqueous PZ solutions are also available up to 63 wt% and 60 °C. CO₂-loaded solution measurements are available for PZ in the open literature, Stec et al. (2016) and Freeman and Rochelle (2011). Density measurements of AMP-PZ blends may be found in the open literature for different AMP/PZ mole ratios, with the AMP concentration going from 15 wt% to 38 wt% and PZ concentrations from 2 wt% to 15 wt% (See supplementary material). However, no density measurements on CO₂-loaded and CO₂-unloaded CESAR1 have been found and these are therefore considered knowledge gaps.

Viscosity is available for aqueous AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ solutions (See supplementary material). Regarding the AMP subsystem, datasets covering the overall range of AMP are available up to 70 °C. No CO₂-loaded viscosity measurements have been found. Viscosity data of aqueous PZ are available up to 63 wt% and 60 °C, and Freeman and Rochelle (2011) measured viscosity in CO₂-loaded piperazine solutions. Viscosity measurements for AMP-PZ blends cover a broad range of concentrations going from 1 to 38 wt% of AMP and 2 to 12 wt% of PZ. Nevertheless, they do not cover the CESAR1 concentration. Furthermore, substantial deviations were discovered between various datasets at the same concentration, making extrapolation from these results difficult. Therefore, viscosity measurements for the CESAR1 solvent are considered an experimental gap.

Surface tension data for aqueous AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ aqueous solution are available in the open literature. Data for CO₂-unloaded AMP solutions have been measured over the whole concentration range and up to 50 °C, showing a decrease in surface tension with amine concentration (Vázquez et al., 1997). Data for CO₂-unloaded piperazine solution have been measured up to 13 wt% PZ and up to 60 °C, showing the same

trend as AMP (Derks et al., 2005b; Murshid et al., 2011). Fu et al. (2013) measured the surface tension of AMP/PZ CO₂-loaded and CO₂-unloaded solutions up to 50 °C, demonstrating that at a fixed PZ concentration, the higher the concentration of AMP, the lower the surface tensions; however, at a fixed AMP concentration, no apparent trend is found with varying PZ concentration. Based on Fu et al. (2013) dataset, higher loadings result in increased surface tension. The CESAR1 surface tension data are not available in the open literature. Murshid et al. (2011) measured the surface tension for AMP/PZ blends, keeping the total concentration of amine constant to 30 wt% and changing the ratio of AMP/PZ between 27/3 wt% and 18/12 wt%. The average surface tension for all blends was 46 N/m, with a standard deviation of 0.5 N/m. This demonstrates that the dependence on the overall ratio is low and that the experimental gap on this property does not hinder proper modelling and sizing of the CO₂ capture plant using the CESAR1 solvent. However, these physical properties may play a role in the amine emission, affecting the growth and the number of aerosol droplets formed in the absorber.

CO₂ physical solubility is another significant physical property for the modelling and simulation of CO₂ capture plants. Physical solubility in terms of Henry's law constant, H_{CO_2} , is often assessed using the N₂O analogy (Monteiro and Svendsen, 2015). The Henry's law constant of CO₂ directly influences the equilibrium model and significantly impacts the kinetics, both affecting the speciation and the evaluation of the kinetic model from experimental data. Using the two-film theory, the observed kinetic constant, k_{obs} , for CO₂ absorption in a pseudo-first-order process may be determined as shown in Eq. (13):

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{H_{\text{CO}_2, \text{solution}}^2}{D_{\text{CO}_2}} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{K_{\text{ov}}} - \frac{1}{k_{\text{G}}} \right)^{-2} \quad (13)$$

Here K_{ov} [m/s] is the overall mass transfer coefficient, k_{G} [m/s] is the gas-side film coefficient, D_{CO_2} [m²/s] is the CO₂ diffusivity in the solvent. Eq. (13) shows that an uncertainty of 20 % in the physical solubility results approximately in an uncertainty of 40 % on the kinetic constant, showing that it is vital to have accurate measurements for the Henry's law constant.

For AMP, Wang et al. (1992) reported the Henry's law constant of CO₂, using the N₂O analogy, in pure AMP solutions up to 81 °C. Tsai et al. (2000), Xu et al. (1991) and Saha et al. (1993) reported Henry's constant of CO₂, using the N₂O analogy, in aqueous AMP solutions, at AMP concentrations up to 3 M (~27 wt%) and temperatures up to 75 °C. Hartono et al. (2020) reported Henry's constant of N₂O in CO₂-loaded solutions of 3 M AMP at temperatures up to 100 °C and three different CO₂-loadings (0.15, 0.35, 0.92 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{AMP}).

For PZ, Sun et al. (2005), Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2007, 2009) reported the Henry's law constant for CO₂, using the N₂O analogy in aqueous PZ solutions, at PZ concentration up to 1.8 M (~15 wt%) and temperature up to 50 °C. Hartono et al. (2021) reported measurements N₂O solubility measurements in CO₂-loaded aqueous PZ solutions at three different concentrations of PZ (~15, 30, 40 wt%) and two CO₂-loadings (0.5 and 0.8 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{PZ}).

For AMP/PZ blends, Samanta and Bandyopadhyay (2009), Khan et al. (2019a) and Sun et al. (2005) reported the Henry's law constant for CO₂ in CO₂-unloaded aqueous AMP/PZ solutions. However, the measurements do not cover the CESAR1 concentration.

Diffusivity is a transport property that affects the mass transfer and the kinetics calculations. Direct measurements of D_{CO_2} in amine aqueous solutions are not possible, and the N₂O analogy is generally adopted. In the open literature, diffusivity measurements have been conducted for AMP, PZ, and AMP/PZ (Khan et al., 2019b; Ko et al., 2001; Sun et al., 2005). Data for AMP are available from 0.5 M to 3 M, while for PZ, data are available from 0.2 M (~1.7 wt%) to 1.4 M (~12 wt%). The datasets are consistent with each other showing a decreasing trend of the CO₂-diffusivity with concentration of AMP and PZ. Data are available for different AMP/PZ ratios, showing a maximum relative error of 9 % (see supplementary material), but not for the CESAR1 concentration.

It can be concluded that there is a need for viscosity and density measurements for CO₂-loaded and CO₂-unloaded CESAR1 concentration. Additionally, it is recommended to measure the physical solubility of CO₂ using the N₂O analogy with the CESAR1 blend.

5. Available degradation data

5.1. Introduction to amine degradation

Aqueous AMP or PZ alone are more stable than aqueous MEA (Buvik et al., 2021b; Eide-Haugmo, 2011; Sexton, 2008; Voice et al., 2013), and so is their blend in the CESAR1 solvent (Campbell et al., 2022; Moser et al., 2023). Although the solvent is very stable under normal operating conditions, it will, like any other organic solvent, degrade during long-term operation. Despite its relatively widespread use, the degradation characteristics of CESAR1 are not fully understood. Many degradation compounds have been identified in the past for both PZ, AMP, and their blend, but it is still unclear whether all products of degradation have indeed been found or if some are still missing, as not all nitrogen lost from the initial amines has successfully been quantified in degradation products. In contrast to MEA, where nearly all nitrogen from lost MEA can be found in its known degradation products (Morken et al., 2014; Vevelstad et al., 2022), Wang and Jens (2014) could account for only 47 % of the nitrogen contained from the start of an oxidative degradation experiment with PZ. Furthermore, Wang (2013) found 53 % of the nitrogen contained in AMP in its identified degradation products. Despite of this, the literature is full of suggested routes and mechanisms of formation of not yet identified degradation products (Eide-Haugmo, 2011; Freeman, 2011; Lepaumier et al., 2009a, 2009b; Nielsen et al., 2013; Wang, 2013; Wang and Jens, 2012, 2014).

Amine degradation is usually divided into categories based on either when or how they are formed in the process, giving rise to the definitions of *primary* and *secondary* degradation compounds. Primary degradation compounds are those that form from the degradation of a single amine molecule, while secondary require more than one amine or amine degradation product molecule to be formed. They are also often divided based on what conditions they are formed under, giving rise to the terms *thermal* and *oxidative* degradation compounds. In reality, the separation between thermal and oxidative degradation products is not clear, and some of the main compounds formed at realistic operating conditions need both heat and oxidising conditions to be formed. On laboratory scale, simplified tests are, however, useful for elucidating solvent behaviour under thermal and oxidative conditions separately. These tests are interesting from a mechanistic point of view when establishing suggested mechanisms of formation, in addition to being very useful for low-cost initial stability testing (Vevelstad et al., 2022).

Characterisation of a degraded solvent requires robust and advanced analytical methodology, as well as skilled operators of said equipment. The combination of several techniques is typically required to identify and quantify all species in a mixture. Freeman and Rochelle (2011, 2012), Wang (2013) and Wang and Jens (2012, 2014) used ion chromatography (IC) for degradation product identification. Lepaumier et al. (2009a, 2009b), Wang (2013) and Wang and Jens (2012, 2014) used IC in addition to gas chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (GCMS). At the pilot campaigns with CESAR1, liquid chromatography with mass spectrometric detection (LCMS), in addition to GC, were used for degradation product identification and quantification (Campbell et al., 2022; Moser et al., 2021a, 2021b).

Some compounds, such as small organic acids, ammonia, and small volatile organic compounds, are expected to be formed in all amine solvents, including CESAR1 and have already been partly identified and quantified in aqueous PZ, AMP, and/or their blend. Some of the most significant and dominant of these are represented in Table 9.

This review article gives an overview of the published data on aqueous AMP, and PZ degradation, alone and blended, including some hy-

Fig. 5. Molecular structure of identified thermal and oxidative degradation products of PZ .

Table 9

List of general degradation compounds that are found or expected in AMP, PZ, and CESAR1.

Compound	CAS number
Ammonia/Ammonium	7664-41-7
Formic acid/Formate	64-18-6
Nitrous acid/Nitrite	7782-77-6
Acetic acid/Acetate	64-19-7
Nitric acid/Nitrate	7697-37-2
Glycolic acid/Glycolate	79-14-1
Oxalic acid/Oxalate	144-62-7

pothetical degradation products presented in the literature, that might become relevant for future studies of CESAR1 degradation.

5.2. Degradation of piperazine (PZ)

Oxidative degradation of amines is typically studied in the laboratory by exposing them to absorber conditions, but mostly by accelerating degradation by using a higher oxygen partial pressure, as well as often adding a metal catalyst (Buvik et al., 2021b; da Silva et al., 2012; Freeman, 2011; Lepaumier et al., 2009b; Vevelstad et al., 2013, 2016). Thermal degradation studies of amines, including PZ, are typically performed in stainless steel cylinders heated to temperatures between 135 and 175 °C, both with and without CO₂ present in the solution (Eide-Haugmo, 2011; Freeman, 2011; Freeman and Rochelle, 2012). From these experiments, both the loss of piperazine and the formation of degradation compounds can be studied, depending on available analytical methodologies.

For PZ, the dominant products to be formed during oxidative degradation seem to be ammonia, formate, oxalate, 1-formylpiperazine (FPZ), and ethylenediamine (EDA), in addition to acetate, nitrate and nitrite in smaller amounts (Freeman, 2011). Although PZ has proven to be very stable under thermal conditions both with and without CO₂ loading (Eide-Haugmo, 2011), the dominant thermal degradation products of aqueous PZ are FPZ, ammonium, *N*-(2-aminoethyl) piperazine (AEP), and 2-imidazolidone (2-imid) (Freeman and Rochelle, 2012). Identified nitrogen containing degradation compounds of PZ are shown in Fig. 5. Although all of these have been identified by at least one analytical method, they have not necessarily all been quantified in degraded PZ.

One of the main concerns in terms of degradation of PZ, being a secondary amine, is that it is prone to form nitrosamines, especially in contact with NO₂ in the flue gas, but also during oxidative degradation in the presence of only O₂. Nitrosamines are a group of carcinogenic compounds containing a -N-N=O functionality. Dai et al. (2012) found that the rate of formation of stable nitrosamines in the presence of NO₂ was much higher in both PZ and an AMP/PZ blend than in MEA. The main nitrosamines formed during PZ degradation are MNPZ and DNPZ, pre-

sented in Fig. 6, but other nitrosamines can theoretically form through nitrosation of any secondary amine degradation product. PZ will typically react with all NO₂ present in the solution to form nitrosamines MNPZ as well as traces of dinitrosopiperazine (DNPZ), which have median toxic doses (TD₅₀) of 8.8 and 3.6 mg/kg/day in rats, respectively (Fine et al., 2013; Fine et al., 2014; Goldman et al., 2013). Due to their toxicity, the nitrosamines must be monitored in wash water, cleaned flue gas and the CO₂ product. MNPZ and DMPZ/DNPZ do, however, decompose at a stripper temperature of 150 °C (Fine et al., 2014) or even as low as 130 °C, but then preferably with a higher stripper pressure (Moser et al., 2023). Contrary to MNPZ, common degradation products of MEA are stable at stripper conditions (Fine et al., 2014). Nitramines, compounds containing a -N-NO₂ moiety, are also potentially carcinogenic compounds that can be formed from any amine in reaction with NO₂, and so that PZ-NO₂, shown in Fig. 6, is therefore also expected to be found in degraded PZ (Silva et al., 2013; Sørensen et al., 2015; White et al., 2015).

Freeman (2011), Freeman and Rochelle (2012), and Wang (2013) also suggested further oxidative and thermal PZ degradation compounds, both non-amines such as methanol, ethanol, and ethylene glycol, as well as amine compounds shown in Fig. 7. Wang (2013) suggested 2-amino-*N*-(2-aminoethyl)-acetamide (AAEA) and *N*-(2-aminoethyl)-2-hydroxy-acetamide (AEHA), depicted Fig. 7, to be intermediate products in the formation of OPZ. For the thermal degradation pathways, Freeman (2011) suggested formation mechanisms of *N*₁-[2-(1-piperazinyl)ethyl]-1,2-ethanediamine (AEAEPZ), 1-[2-(1-piperazinyl)ethyl]-2-imidazolidinone (AEAEPZ urea), and *N*-[2-(1-piperazinyl)ethyl]-1-piperazineethanamine (PEPA), 1-piperazineethanamine (AEP), EDA, and 1,1'-(1,2-ethanediyl)bis-piperazine (PEP), all shown in Fig. 7. They also suggested S_N2 reactions with AEAEPZ reacting further to longer chained PZ derivatives such as APEE, PolyAEP, and APAE. None of the depicted compounds have been unambiguously identified in degraded PZ yet.

Compared to MEA, PZ undergoes very little oxidative degradation at absorber conditions but forms nitrosamines which then can decompose at stripper conditions, causing oxidative degradation in the stripper rather than the absorber (Farmer et al., 2019). It can also degrade with dissolved oxygen in the stripper, especially in the presence of dissolved metals (Cousins et al., 2015; Rochelle et al., 2011; Wu and Rochelle, 2021).

5.3. Degradation of 2-methyl-2-amino-1-propanol (AMP)

Oxidative and thermal degradation studies of AMP are done analogously to those of PZ. Wang (2013) presents a thorough study of AMP stability. The main products of oxidative AMP degradation were found to be acetone, 2,4-lutidine (LUT), 4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazolidinone (DMOZD), formate, oxalate, acetate, glycolate, ni-

Fig. 6. Nitrosamines and nitramines of piperazine.

Fig. 7. Further PZ degradation compounds and intermediates suggested by Freeman, Freeman and Rochelle, and Wang (Freeman, 2011; Freeman and Rochelle, 2012; Wang, 2013).

trite, nitrate, and ammonia, and it was found that increasing the CO₂ loading of the solution increased the oxidative degradation rate of AMP. Lepaumier et al. (2009b) also found 2-methyl-2-(methylamino)-1-propanol (*N*-methyl AMP) to be one of the main oxidative degradation compounds of AMP. Thermal AMP degradation produces DMOZD, 2-[(2-amino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-2-methyl-1-propanol (AMPAMP), 4,4-dimethyl-1-hydroxytertiobutyl-2-imidazolidinone (DMHTBI), *N*-methyl AMP, and 3,4,4-trimethyl-2-oxazolidinone (TMOZD) (Eide-Haugmo, 2011; Lepaumier et al., 2009a;

Wang, 2013) shown in Fig. 8. Other suggested AMP degradation compounds are depicted in Fig. 9.

AMP can also be expected to form nitrosamine, although to a much smaller extent than PZ, since it is a primary amine. This means that AMP will have to form a secondary amine, such as *N*-methyl AMP first before nitrosation can take place and formation of *N*-nitroso-AMP, shown in Fig. 10, is possible. More concerning than AMP forming nitrosamine, is that AMP usually comes with some *N*-methyl AMP when purchased (Languille et al., 2021a), meaning that the contaminant in the fresh

Fig. 8. Identified nitrogen containing oxidative and thermal degradation products of AMP degradation (Eide-Haugmo, 2011; Eide-Haugmo et al., 2011; Lepaumier et al., 2009a, 2009b; Wang, 2013).

Fig. 9. Suggested AMP degradation compounds (Davis, 2009; Eide-Haugmo, 2011; Wang, 2013).

Fig. 10. Likely nitrosamine and nitramine formed from AMP.

amine may react to form *N*-nitroso AMP. AMP can also form a corresponding nitramine, AMP-NO₂.

5.4. Degradation of AMP/PZ blends

Oxidative degradation of a blend of AMP and PZ resulted in the identification of already known degradation compounds from the individual amines; acetone, EDA, DMOZD, 2,4-lutidine, FPZ, OPZ, formate, acetate, and oxalate, as well as small quantities of glycolate, nitrate, MNPZ, and the new degradation product 1,4-diformylpiperazine (DFP) depicted in Fig. 11 (Wang, 2013). Thermal degradation of AMP/PZ blends results in *N*-methylpiperazine (MPZ), AMPAMP, AEP, and DMHTBI, in addition to the new compounds 1,4-di(2-aminoethyl) piperazine (DAEP), and *N,N'*-dimethylpiperazine (DMP) in Fig. 11 (Wang, 2013). They, however, showed that the oxidative degradation rate of AMP increased in the presence of PZ, which aligns with the common trend that blends tend to degrade faster than their individual components (Rochelle, 2012). A condensation product of AMP and PZ, 1,1-dimethyl-2-piperazine-1-ethylamine (CAS: 1259927-55-3), has been suggested to form during degradation of the blend (Li et al., 2013).

Pilot scale CESAR1 campaigns have proven to produce the following AMP and PZ degradation compounds during operation: NH₃, LUT, DMOZD, MNPZ, OPZ, EDA, formate, propionate, oxalate, acetate, and glycolate (Campbell et al., 2022; Moser et al., 2023). A typical behaviour for aqueous MEA under large-scale tests with real flue gases is that it typically reaches an autocatalytic exponential degradation range, where degradation rate increases very rapidly, ultimately leading to a need for campaign interruption due to uncontrollable degradation. This behaviour has not yet been observed with CESAR1, where even operation for 3 years without solvent replacement showed a relatively slow and steady degradation rate (Moser et al., 2023). In this, above mentioned 3-year long CESAR1 pilot testing, formate, oxalate, propionate, acetate, glycolate, EDA, FPZ, and OPZ were quantified in the blend throughout the campaign (Moser et al., 2021, 2023). Technology Centre Mongstad (TCM) in Norway also ran a pilot campaign with CESAR1 on flue gas from both a combined heat and power plant (CHP), and a residue fluid catalytic cracker (RFCC) source (Campbell et al., 2022). There, LUT, DMOZD, MNPZ, and OPZ were quantified in the used solvent throughout the campaign, in addition to total nitrosamine content. Using a higher stripper temperature could reduce nitrosamine concentrations, reduce the overall energy demand of the stripper, and lower the capital costs for both the compressors and the stripper Rochelle (2012). However, it also results in faster degradation and an increased need for amine makeup. However, there is a shortage of data on CESAR1 degradation and the VLE behaviour at temperatures above 120 °C, to explore the opportunities and challenges of high-temperature stripping.

Identification and quantification of all possible degradation products of CESAR1 will make the operation safer and facilitate the assessment of environmental risks and is, therefore, an important knowledge gap to close.

Fig. 11. Products of oxidative and thermal degradation of an AMP and PZ blend (Wang, 2013).

5.5. Degradation management

Although CESAR1 degradation appears to be slow and not so problematic for the CO₂ capture process as is observed with other amines like MEA, it does degrade, and it can be expected that implementation of solvent management strategies will be necessary for full-scale long-term CO₂ capture operations. Moser et al. (2023) demonstrated three different management strategies during their 3 year-long campaign at Niederaussem;

- Removal of heat stable salts (HSS) by ion exchange
- Adsorptive removal of contaminants by active carbon
- Thiosulfate/sulphite pre-treatment of the flue gas for NO₂ removal prior to liquid CO₂ absorption

None of these strategies successfully decreased the solvent degradation rate, which seemed to be at its slowest when the solvent had been in operation for 77–216 days, without any management technology implementations. Campbell et al. (2022) describes how Technology Centre Mongstad (TCM) successfully performed thermal reclaiming of a CESAR1 solvent that had been in use for the first 1600, and then for additional 2200 h in a semi-continuous operation mode. This approach successfully removed >80 % of all unknown degradation products, including HSS, as well as > 90 % of the metals dissolved in the solvent and the loss of amine was <5 %.

There is still research needed to understand both *when* and *how* to perform solvent degradation management strategies such as reclamation on CESAR1, as the solvent is very stable compared to, i.e., aqueous MEA. Aiming to keep the solvent “clean”, free of contaminants and degradation products, does not seem to be a good strategy to keep degradation rates low (Buvik et al., 2023; Moser et al., 2023), so the decision to implement, i.e., solvent reclaiming, should probably be based on other operational challenges such as reduced CO₂ capture capacity instead.

6. Pilot studies

6.1. Pilot campaigns with AMP/PZ blends

As of today, testing of aqueous blends of AMP and PZ at nine different pilot sites is reported in the literature. The main test conditions and results from the tests are listed Table 10. Extended data for these pilot tests, where data from tests with 30 wt% MEA in the respective pilots are available in the Supplementary material.

In all pilot tests, CO₂ from real flue gases was captured. However, the dimensions and configurations of the pilot sites are different. In addition, the pilot campaigns were operated with different targets or research goals, covering a large variety of test conditions and parameters. The duration of the pilot testing varies from days to years. Therefore, clear conclusions of the campaign outcomes by direct comparison of the pilot tests cannot be drawn. On the other hand, the differences in the tests and their results can be used to identify the need for duplications as well as new types of tests to close knowledge gaps related to process modelling, operational conditions and challenges when intending to use CESAR1 as the solvent in large-scale post-combustion CO₂ capture. First, general observations and findings across the pilot tests are described and discussed, followed by a qualitative assessment of data gaps in the CESAR1 piloting.

The amine concentration and the AMP/PZ ratio in most of the pilot tests deviate somewhat from the CESAR1 definition, although several of

the test publications use the solvent term CESAR1. The reported AMP concentrations in the tests were in the 25.0 – 28.8 wt% range Table 10. The PZ concentration is observed to have a broader range in the tests, spanning from 5 to 17 wt%. In three pilot test publications, the statement on the amine concentration used is missing (Hume et al., 2021; Mejdell et al., 2022; Tatarczuk et al., 2015).

The amine concentration is typically monitored throughout the campaign. However, most of the publications do not specify how often the solvent concentration was monitored. Furthermore, limited information and data are available about the solvent loss and solvent concentration change during the pilot operation. This information is necessary to estimate the amine makeup needed and the costs associated with it and constitutes an additional knowledge gap in the current literature. The variety might stem from concentration fluctuations during the operation and testing. For the CESAR1 pilot test at TCM Mongstad, the analyses were carried out before and during the campaign, revealing shifts both in total amine concentration and AMP/PZ ratio from the target solvent concentration of 27 wt% AMP and 13 wt% PZ (Akhter et al., 2022). The low PZ concentration in the test performed at the CSIRO pilot plant was intentionally limited to 5 % to avoid any operational problems due to the formation of solid precipitates, which might occur at higher amine or PZ concentrations (Artanto et al., 2014). The undesired precipitation in AMP/PZ at higher amine and CO₂ concentrations is further discussed in the section “Operational challenges”.

6.1.1. Flue gas CO₂ concentration in pilot testing

In the process of chemical CO₂ absorption, the CO₂ concentration in the flue gas affects the magnitude of energy needed to regenerate the solvent. The energy demand is seen to be lower for high flue gas CO₂ concentrations. The decrease in energy demand with increasing CO₂ concentration is mainly caused by the higher CO₂ partial pressure, which increases the driving forces leading to higher CO₂ loadings in the rich solvent (Li et al., 2011; Li et al., 2011). The flue gas at the pilot sites is provided from the combustion of different fossil fuels, commonly coal or gas. Some pilots are connected to more than one flue gas source. TCM, Mongstad, for instance, can operate with either the combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) based heat and power plant flue gas (CHP) or residual fluid catalytic cracker (RFCC) flue gas (Akhter et al., 2022) from the Mongstad refinery. The SINTEF Tiller pilot is constructed to capture CO₂ from flue gases either from a propane burner or coal or biomass burner (Aronu et al., 2021). Recycling of the CO₂ product gas is also an option at the TCM, Mongstad, and SINTEF Tiller pilots, enabling an increase in CO₂ concentration in the flue gas. Lower CO₂ concentrations can be achieved by diluting the feed flue gas with air. The AMP/PZ pilot tests with the lowest CO₂ concentrations in the flue gas, i.e., 3.5 vol%, wet, and 5 vol%, dry, were performed at TCM, Mongstad during two different campaigns (Benquet et al., 2021; Hume et al., 2021). The campaign at Kaiserslautern also operated with flue gas CO₂ content in the low range (54 mbar) (Mangalapally and Hasse, 2011a). The remaining AMP/PZ pilot campaigns were operated with CO₂ concentrations ≥10 %, with 15.2 vol%, dry, as the highest in the test at RWE Power, Niederaussem (Moser et al., 2021).

6.1.2. Capture rates and energy performance

In the pilot tests of the aqueous blends of AMP and PZ, the most common capture rate applied was around 90 %. The CESAR1 campaign at TCM, Mongstad aimed to examine the energy consumption penalty

Fig. 12. Comparison between MEA and AMP/PZ in SRD in pilot tests (see Supplementary material). The operating conditions were kept similar for the two solvents within each pilot test. References: DONG Energy, Esbjerg, DK (Knudsen et al., 2011, 2009), University of Kaiserslautern, DE (Mangalapally and Hasse, 2011a, 2011b), CSIRO PCC pilot plant Loy Yang, AU (Artanto et al., 2012, 2014), Jaworzno, PL (Tatarczuk et al., 2015), CO₂SEPPL, Graz, AT (Rabensteiner et al., 2016), TCM, Mongstad, NO *CO₂ content in flue gas: 3.5 %, wet and 3.6 %, dry, in CESAR1 and MEA test, respectively (Benquet et al., 2021; Faramarzi et al., 2017) TCM, Mongstad, NO **CO₂ content in flue gas: 14 and 13 - 14 %, dry, in CESAR1 and MEA test, respectively (Hume et al., 2022, 2021), RWE Power, Niederaussem, DE (Moser et al., 2020, 2021), SINTEF Tiller, Trondheim, NO (Flø et al., 2016; Mejdell et al., 2022).

The tests with the NMPC demonstrated that the pilot plant and the CESAR1 solvent could handle changes in flue gas flow from 130 to 340 m³/h without operational challenges. Disturbances in the CO₂ concentration were also well managed by the NMPC system. A smooth transfer from one capture rate to another could be obtained from 85 % up to 99 % capture rate without any significant increase in the SRD, as mentioned previously. This study demonstrated that using a dynamic real-time optimiser with the CESAR1 solvent can minimise the capture cost over a longer horizon, which can benefit, e.g., power plants operating with cyclic variations.

6.2. Operational challenges

During piloting, issues in solvent behaviour might occur that do not appear in laboratory and small-scale or short-term testing. Two main operational challenges were observed during CESAR1 pilot testing, namely solvent precipitation and foaming. These phenomena depend on several factors that may vary within a pilot plant and between the different pilot plants. The identification and handling of foaming and precipitation during CESAR1 pilot tests are described in the next two sections. Moser et al. (2023) stated that no corrosion issue was observed during their 3-year pilot campaign. They did not employ any corrosion inhibitors, and no reclaiming activities were performed. Finally, they found that the CESAR1 solvent is less corrosive than MEA.

6.2.1. Precipitation

The aqueous AMP/PZ solution precipitates upon higher concentrations of AMP or PZ, higher total amine concentration and higher CO₂ loading. The solids might clog lines and equipment in a capture plant and thereby cause severe operational problems. Therefore, it is essential to identify the operational window where precipitation is avoided. Brüder et al. (2011) performed screening laboratory testing for precipitation of different ratios of the AMP/PZ in aqueous solution, with a variation in total amine concentration and CO₂ loading. The AMP/PZ ratio of 3/1.5 M, corresponding to the CESAR1 definition, was identified as the highest possible, at which no precipitation occurs during the absorption of CO₂ at 40 °C. The maximum loading for this specific AMP/PZ ratio was reported to be 0.58 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{amine}.

In the pilot testing of the AMP/PZ blends, precipitation was reported only for some of the tests at TCM, Mongstad (Akhter et al., 2022; Benquet et al., 2021). Prior to the initiation of the first CESAR1

pilot campaign at TCM, Mongstad, in 2019, laboratory tests were carried out to examine CESAR1 precipitation at different CO₂ loading and temperature (Benquet et al., 2021). Three CESAR1 samples were prepared: one rich loaded with 0.73 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{amine}, one lean loaded with 0.10 mol_{CO₂}/mol_{amine} and one unloaded. Each sample was subsequently divided into three parts and exposed to 4, 25 and 40 °C. The rich sample precipitated at all three temperatures. Gel was observed in the lean and unloaded samples only at 4 °C. To further examine the loading levels for precipitation, the rich sample was diluted with unloaded CESAR1 to yield 0.61 mole CO₂/mole amine. For this sample, no precipitation occurred at 40 and 23 °C. However, precipitation did occur at 7 °C after 48 h. Despite considering the laboratory precipitation test results upon CESAR1 pilot testing, precipitation at TCM, Mongstad was identified by a differential pressure increase in the lower absorber packing when the flue gas was conditioned to 30 °C (Benquet et al., 2021). The pressure drop was accompanied by an estimated 29 % loss of the total amine mass by analysing amine concentration in lean solvent samples without any leakages found in the plant. No precipitation was observed when the tests were run with a flue gas inlet temperature of 40 °C. In a subsequent CESAR1 campaign at TCM, Mongstad, the increasing differential pressure across the lower absorber packing was a recurring problem, even with a flue gas temperature of 40 °C (Akhter et al., 2022). The authors assign the TCM absorber design as a likely contributing cause of the CESAR1 precipitation. The absorber has a rectangular cross-section, over which the solvent temperature and concentrations may vary. The concrete absorber walls are not insulated, and poor gas distribution at the corners and walls might cause local accumulation of CESAR1 precipitation.

6.2.2. Foaming

The occurrence of foaming has been reported for two pilots during the AMP/PZ aqueous blend test, namely RWE Power, Niederaussem, and TCM (Akhter et al., 2022; Hume et al., 2022, 2021; Moser et al., 2021, 2023). Upon pilot testing of CESAR1 at RWE Power, Niederaussem, a commercial anti-foaming agent was added upon incipient foaming, indicated by fluctuations of the differential pressure in the stripper column. There, foaming did not cause significant operational issues. At TCM Mongstad, the CESAR1 foaming led to unstable stripper operation, identified by analysis of the stripper temperature profiles (Akhter et al., 2022). The foaming tendency was experienced as unpredictable. Even with fresh solvent, the foaming could start some hours after plant start-

up, with both increasing and decreasing tendencies. In the worst cases of foaming, the SRD could increase up to 0.25 GJ/ton CO₂. The addition of an anti-foam removed foaming to a certain level, resulting in lower steam requirements in the reboiler and, thereby, lower SRD. However, the duration of the anti-foam effect could be limited to a few hours only. The type of anti-foam used at TCM was not reported. Therefore, the anti-foam effect cannot be evaluated by comparison with RWE Power, Niederaussem.

6.3. Qualitative assessment of data gaps in CESAR1 piloting

The CO₂ content in the flue gas in CESAR1 piloting was in the range of ~4 – 5 and ~10 – 15 vol%, dry. Most of the tests operated with a CO₂ concentration in the higher range. This covers a wide range of industrial applications which will require decarbonization. However, no tests were conducted with flue gases where the CO₂ concentration is very low, i.e., 1 – 3 %, such as from aluminium production (Wang and Song, 2020). Such a low flue gas CO₂ partial pressure might induce a significant energy penalty. Determining the SRD for flue gases with the lowest contents of CO₂ with CESAR1 pilot testing is important for both OPEX assessments and process model validation. For the same reasons, the CESAR1 solvent performance with flue gases from industrial plants with much higher concentrations of CO₂, i.e., ~15 – 30 %, such as from steel, cement and hydrogen production (Wang and Song, 2020) should also be evaluated by pilot testing, although a high deviation in SRD is not expected.

In the early days of CCS research, a capture rate of around 90 % of the CO₂ from flue gases was deemed acceptable, and piloting campaigns, therefore, typically targeted this in the earlier tests. Currently, it is predicted that in net-zero emission energy systems, capture rates approaching 100 % are required to effectively mitigate global warming exceeding 1.5 or 2 °C (IEA, 2020). The few CESAR1 pilot tests that operated at a capture rate of 98 % demonstrated an SRD increase of about 10 % compared to the 90 % case. However, the difference in SRD could be minimized to 3 % using an advanced control system, as reported by (Mejdell et al., 2022). Therefore, long-term performance of CESAR1 should target capture rates >98 %.

Power and industrial plant operations have regular or irregular shut-down and start-up scenarios that will require dynamic operation of the CO₂ capture plant. An advanced control system should be tested in a CESAR1 operated pilot with varying frequencies of such scenarios to examine how optimal operational conditions can be achieved.

CESAR1 precipitation can be specifically challenging for the bottom of the absorber, where fast evaporation of water when the flue gas is contacted with the solvent can lead to an up-concentrated AMP + PZ solution forming solids. The results from laboratory experiments carried out at TCM to examine the CESAR1 precipitation tendency between 4 and 40 °C did not necessarily predict the solids formation during solvent loading and operation. Therefore, a precipitation-safe operational window must be established by pilot testing CESAR1 with flue gas temperatures in the 35 – 40 °C range. Factors leading to foaming are not obvious, although high stripper temperature, impurities in the flue gas, solvent properties, particles of solids and corrosion, and the design of stripper column internals are all suspected to be potential causes. There are no reports on systematic investigations on the type of anti-foaming agents, minimum injection rates, injection intervals, or if there is any effect of long-term anti-foam dosing on CESAR1.

6.4. Pilot studies with the single amines

The single amine components of CESAR1 have also been studied on a pilot scale, and PZ stands out as more tested than AMP. One pilot campaign was run at NTNU in Norway with 2.8–2.9 M AMP (aq.) with the purpose of experimentally validating a rate-based model using synthetic flue gas (Gabrielsen, 2007; Gabrielsen et al., 2007). The earliest PZ pilot studies were run at the Separation Research Programme (SRP) pilot

(Chen et al., 2014, 2013) and Pilot Plant 2 (PP2) (Nielsen et al., 2013) in USA, and the Tarong CO₂ capture pilot plant in Australia (Cousins et al., 2012, 2015a, 2015b), the first capturing CO₂ from a synthetic flue gas and the two latter from coal-fired power plant flue gas. These campaigns were run with 30–40 wt% PZ (aq.). In the USA, the aqueous PZ solvent has been thoroughly tested at different scales, in the trademarked Piperazine with Advanced Stripper (PZASTM) process, including on flue gas from a coal-fired power plant and a Natural Gas Combined Cycle (NGCC) process at the National Carbon Capture Center (NCCC) (Rochelle et al., 2022; Suresh Babu and Rochelle, 2022). PZ has thereby been thoroughly tested, with energy optimisation, degradation, and emission studies, and with high CO₂ capture rates.

6.5. Emissions

Real-time online measurement of emissions from CO₂ capture plants is complemented by impinger samples of flue gas components over time. Most commonly Fourier-transform infrared detection (FTIR) is used for the analysis (Buvik et al., 2021; Drageset et al., 2022; Languille et al., 2021b; Morken et al., 2014, 2017; Silva et al., 2013), but its limits of quantification (LOQ) of around 1 ppm can be a challenge (Drageset et al., 2022), meaning that other analytical methods are implemented to complement and potentially replace FTIR as the most important monitoring technology. More advanced on-line analytical tools have been tested by TCM, such as proton-transfer-reaction time-of-flight mass spectrometer (PTR-MS-TOF), PTR quadrupole mass spectrometer (PTR-QMS) and IMR-MS (ion-molecule reaction mass spectrometer) to ensure that they can detect and quantify within the range of upper emission limits for all possible compounds in the flue gas (Drageset et al., 2022; Languille et al., 2021a, 2021b). All the latter techniques can quantify down to ppb-levels, where the PTR-MS-TOF and PTR-QMS have the lowest LOQs. The IMR-MS has successfully been validated for monitoring of the AMP concentrations with high accuracy, while PZ, ammonia and acetone are detected, but not yet reliably quantified by the method (Drageset et al., 2022). As this technique is relatively new in the field, and still under testing and validation, one can however hope that these and more degradation compounds can be reliably quantified in the future, as the instrumentation as well as the data processing of the IMR-MS are simpler than for the PTR methods (Drageset et al., 2022).

AMP is much more volatile than PZ and is, therefore, the dominant species present in the cleaned flue gas, often in 1–2 orders of magnitude higher than PZ, during operations with CESAR1 (Languille et al., 2021a; Spietz et al., 2020). An efficient water-wash system is crucial to avoid AMP-contaminated CO₂-free flue gas exiting the plant and can bring down the solvent emissions dramatically, Languille et al. (2021a) obtained levels between 562 and 377 ppb. Spietz et al. (2024) reported that the concentration of AMP in the treated gas exceeded the instrument range (Gaset DX4000 FTIR), > 200 ppm, and was reduced to 15–25 ppm after a 3-stage water wash section of 0.81 m.

As previously stated, nitrosamines and nitramines are some of the largest concerns, in terms of CO₂ capture plant emissions, as these groups of carcinogenic compounds are formed during amine solvent degradation. In CESAR1, PZ is particularly prone to the formation of nitrosamines, as secondary amines can be readily nitrosated. The main nitrosamine compound formed through nitrosation of PZ is MNPZ, but further variations such as DNPZ or nitrosated secondary amine degradation compounds can also be present. The advantage of, i.e., MNPZ (Fig. 6) over the main MEA-derived nitrosamine N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA) is that it is much less volatile, making it less likely for it to escape the absorber column with the cleaned flue gas. AMP can also form nitrosamines during the process, and PZ and AMP both can form nitramines, that all need monitoring in the cleaned flue gas. Nitrosamines undergo photolytic degradation upon irradiation, i.e., in sunlight, meaning that emissions of MNPZ or DNPZ will eventually decompose (Sørensen et al., 2015). If emitted during the daytime, the

Fig. 13. Compounds detected and quantified in the cleaned flue gas from TCM's CESAR1 pilot campaign (Languille et al., 2021a).

nitrosamines may accumulate less in the environment, due to photolytic degradation in the air.

A thorough test study was performed at the TCM performing CO₂ capture from the CHP flue gas, investigating the emissions created from pilot operation with the CESAR1 solvent (Languille et al., 2021a, 2021b). A PTR-TOF-MS identified and quantified solvent amine, 10 amine degradation products and 1 solvent contaminant online in the cleaned flue gas. With two water wash sections, mean and median AMP emissions were 562 and 377 ppb, and PZ in the 1 ppb range. Of the degradation products, acetone is the most dominant in the emissions, which coincides with Wang (2013) encountering acetone as a major AMP and AMP/PZ blend degradation product. The acetone concentration was in the same range as AMP. Formaldehyde and acetaldehyde, shown in Fig. 13, were emitted in lower concentrations, in the range of approximately 10–200 ppb. Other degradation products found in the emissions were acetonitrile, formamide, DMO (shown in Fig. 8), methylamine, morpholine, 4-acetylmorpholine. They also identified a compound with the molecular formula C₈H₁₄N₂, which can be an alkylated imidazole or pyrazole. The typical AMP contaminant 2-methyl-2-(methylamino)propan-1-ol was also found in the emissions from the plant. Nitrosamines could not be quantified in the cleaned flue gas during this study, and the authors concluded that their concentration was below 1 ppb, although they could detect the presence of MNPZ.

7. Environmental impacts of CESAR1

For the use of amine solvents for large-scale CO₂ capture, any possible environmental impact of the process must be considered. Their possible effects on the health of humans and other organisms are the most important assessment criteria. If a compound persists in the environment without undergoing enzymatic decomposition, or biodegradation, it will accumulate in the biota and may cause adverse long-term effects on the environment. In addition to biodegradation or accumulation, it is also important to consider direct toxic effects or health effects on living organisms. Environmental persistence is typically tested by adding the test substance to an unpolluted fresh or saltwater sample enriched with inorganic nutrients, in a closed bottle, and determining biotic degradation by measuring oxygen consumption. Ecotoxicity is performed by inoculation of a test organism with test substance and by any suitable means studying its growth or mortality.

7.1. Toxicity and exposure limits

Except for the fact that degradation may change the composition of CESAR1, toxicity assessments are based on the individual components of

the solvent. Both amines are naturally corrosive, due to their alkalinity. PZ is considered more harmful to human health than AMP, additionally being flammable and labelled with a health hazard pictogram as it is suspected to harm fertility, and possibly the unborn child. The Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH) recommends lower upper exposure limits for different amines and here, the limit of exposure is lower for PZ than MEA in the air in general, as shown in Table 11 (Låg et al., 2009). For AMP the upper exposure limit is unclear, but according to NILU it is at least higher than 6 µg/m³ (Låg et al., 2011). There are no recommendations for occupational exposure limits of AMP yet.

Since the amines degrade during operation and it is expected that a used solvent will contain not just AMP, PZ, and water, one should also look at the toxicity of some of their degradation compounds. Being a carcinogenic group, the nitrosamines are often highlighted of most concern next to the amines themselves (Låg et al., 2009, 2011). For the construction of Technology Centre Mongstad, NIPH concluded that the sum of total nitramine and nitrosamine concentration in the air should not exceed 0.3 ng/m³, to ensure no significant increase in risk of cancer in the population (Låg et al., 2011). This number was calculated based on the carcinogenicity of the MEA-derived nitrosamine NDMA. In Table 12 the toxicity of some of the known nitrosamines and nitramines of the CESAR1 components, as well as some of the components of MEA are listed. Although PZ is considered more toxic than MEA, its most abundant nitrosamine MNPZ has an almost 100 times higher median toxic dose (TD₅₀) than NDMA, one of the MEA derived nitrosamines. The nitramines generally exhibit lower toxicity than the nitrosamines, and both AMP-NO₂, and PZ-NO₂ show no evidence of mutagenic activity (Dye et al., 2011). Table 12 also gives the 10⁻⁶ cancer risk of some of the nitrosamines, and is an exposure limit for i.e., nitrosamine in drinking water and long-term exposure. The concentration given is that at which the risk of developing cancer because of the exposure exceeds 1 in one million, which is a defined limit for a non-negligible effect. The tolerable limit for exposure of piperazine derived nitrosamines is also here, much higher than the MEA derived NDMA. No data could be found for nitramine of PZ, or nitrosamine and nitramine of AMP.

7.2. Ecotoxicity and biodegradation

Ecotoxicity and biodegradability of AMP and PZ, as well as MEA (for reference) are given in Table 13 and were both experimentally determined by Eide-Haugmo et al. (2012). Ecotoxicity was measured in the marine phytoplankton species *Skeletonema costatum* is defined as the effective concentration (EC) that inhibits the growth of the species by 50 % (EC₅₀). Biodegradability was performed by the same authors following

Table 11
Toxicity of and recommended exposure limits of the amine components of CESAR1 compared to MEA for reference (Låg et al., 2009,2011).

	MEA	AMP	PZ
General upper long-term exposure limit in air [µg/m ³]	10	> 6	5
Occupational exposure limit, 8 h in air [mg/m ³]	2.5	–	0.1
Occupational exposure limit short-term: 15 min [mg/m ³]	7.6	–	0.3
Median lethal dose (LD ₅₀) in rats [g/kg _{bodyweight}]	1.1 - 2.7	2.9	1 - 5

Table 12

Toxicity of Nitrosamines and nitramines deriving from PZ, AMP, or MEA. TD₅₀ in rat or mouse (CPDB, 2023; Garcia et al., 1970; Låg et al., 2011). Limit exceeding 10⁻⁶ cancer risk as exposure in air or water (EPA, 1987; Harju et al., 2011; Mazari et al., 2019).

Compound	CAS-number	Derivative of	Median toxic dose (TD ₅₀), [mg/kg _{bodyweight} /day]	10 ⁻⁶ cancer risk concentration [ng/L]
N-nitrosodimethylamine (NDMA)	62-75-9	MEA	0.096	0.7
N-nitrosodiethanolamine (NDELA)	1116-54-7	MEA	3.2 – 3.7	0.08
N-Nitromethylamine	598-57-2	MEA	17.4	-
N-Nitrodimethylamine	4164-28-7	MEA	0.54	-
N-Nitrosopiperazine (MNPZ)	5632-47-3	PZ	8.8	140
Dinitrosopiperazine (DNPZ)	140-79-4	PZ	3.6	10

Table 13

Ecotoxicity and biodegradability of the components of CESAR1, as well as MEA (Eide-Haugmo et al., 2012). EC₅₀ in *S. costatum* has a confidence interval of ±95 %.

Compound	EC ₅₀ [mg/L]	BOD28 (% of ThOD)
PZ	472	3
AMP	119	<1
MEA	198	68

Table 14

Ecotoxicity of various nitramines, with ±95 % confidence interval, defined as inhibition of *P. subcapitata* growth rate (EC₅₀) and mortality of *D. magna* (LC₅₀) (Dye et al., 2011).

Nitramine	EC ₅₀ [mg/L]	LC ₅₀ [mg/L]	BOD28 (% of ThOD)
PZ-NO ₂	430	1423	3
AMP-NO ₂	871	2408	20
MEA-NO ₂	2535	>2500	33

OECD guideline 306 (OECD, 1992b) and is defined as biological oxygen demand (BOD) from measured oxygen concentration after 28 days of incubation in closed bottles (BOD28). A theoretical oxygen demand was calculated based on the chemical formula of the compounds by degradation into NH₃ and a high BOD28 corresponds to high biodegradability.

The amine components of CESAR1 are not just more stable in the process itself but will also persist in the environment longer than MEA. As opposed to the process stability, a low biodegradability is not a desirable characteristic of an amine, and neither is the higher ecotoxicity exhibited by AMP and PZ compared to MEA. No nitrosamine ecotoxicity or biodegradation studies could be found in the literature, but atmospheric decomposition studies have been performed. Nitrosamines readily photodegrade, while nitramines do not (Sørensen et al., 2015). Ecotoxicity of nitramines was experimentally determined in the green algae *Pseudokirchneriella subcapitata*, and the marine invertebrate *Daphnia magna* by Dye et al. (2011). In Table 14 the results from the tests with PZ-NO₂, AMP-NO₂ and MEA-NO₂ are given as EC₅₀ for growth inhibition of *P. subcapitata* and lethal concentrations (LC) of nitramine to cause mortal-

Property	AMP/H ₂ O	PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O	AMP/H ₂ O/CO ₂	PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂	AMP/PZ/H ₂ O/CO ₂
Density	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Not available at CESAR1 concentration
Viscosity	Green	Green	Not available at CESAR1 concentration	Not available	Green	Not available at CESAR1 concentration
Diffusivity	Green	Yellow	Not available at CESAR1 concentration	Not available	Not available	Not available
Kinetics	Green	Green	Not available at CESAR1 concentration	Not available	Green	Not available
VLE	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Data available at lower concentrations but not with different AMP/PZ ratio
CO ₂ Henry's constant	Green	Green	Not available at CESAR1 concentration	Green	Data not available at low CO ₂ loading	Not available
Speciation	Green	Green	Green	Green	Green	Not available at CESAR1 concentration
Degradation	Some data is available, but N-balance is still open meaning that unidentified/unquantified degradation products exist.					
ΔH _{abs}	Green			High inconsistency between the datasets	Green	Green

Fig. 14. Summary of the main experimental gaps. Legend: Data unavailable (red), Gaps identified (yellow), Data available (green). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article).

ity of 50 % of *D. magna* (LC₅₀). Biodegradability was established using OECD guideline 301D (Dye et al., 2011; OECD, 1992a), and was defined as biological oxygen demand (BOD) from measured oxygen concentration after 28 days of incubation in closed bottles (BOD28), assuming nitrogen is turned into NO₂.

PZ-NO₂ is both more ecotoxic and less biodegradable in the environment than AMP-NO₂, and the reference, MEA-NO₂. The low BOD28 indicates high bioaccumulation, especially for PZ-NO₂, if it forms and is emitted to the environment.

8. Summary of the key findings and conclusions

Experimental gaps for physical, kinetics and thermodynamic properties, as well as degradation chemical pathways for AMP and PZ, have been identified within this literature review. A summary of the results of this work is given in Fig. 14. Physical properties data are available for AMP/PZ aqueous blend, but gaps at the CESAR1 concentration have been detected. Thermodynamic properties such as vapour-liquid equilibrium and heat of absorption data are available at CESAR1 concentration, experimental investigations at lower AMP/PZ concentration at different ratios are suggested to properly model aerosol formation and design the water wash section. Kinetics measurements for CO₂ loaded AMP and AMP/PZ aqueous solutions are not available even though they directly impact the absorption performance. Speciation and N₂O-solubility data at CESAR1 concentration are not available in the open literature, but measurements are suggested for rigorous thermodynamic modelling.

A review of the currently found and hypothesized **degradation** compounds for AMP and PZ aqueous solutions has been presented. However, the nitrogen balance for AMP and PZ is not closed, meaning that there still are compounds that need identification and quantification in the degraded solvent. Once the nitrogen balance of the solvent is closed, one can start investigating the impact the known degradation products can have on operation, and environment, and thereby develop monitoring and mitigation strategies that are optimal for the CESAR1 solvent.

Several **pilot campaigns** have been performed. They show that CESAR1 performs better in terms of energy compared to MEA and degrades less. Further, CESAR1 seems to be suitable for high capture rates and can be operated over long periods of time without reclaiming. However, there is a need for high-quality pilot campaigns where all data needed for process model validation is provided for the scientific community.

To control solvent and degradation component emissions mitigation technologies and more monitoring compared to MEA is needed. AMP is more volatile than MEA and as the system's chemistry is complex, a better understanding of the formation and behaviour of potential aerosol emissions is needed by performing focused pilot campaigns and developing aerosol models specific for CESAR1.

Exposure limits and limits for nitrosamine and nitramine content in air and drinking water based on NDMA, which seems much more toxic than the PZ and AMP derived nitrosamines and nitramines. Current limits seem, therefore, to ensure that the risks will be low.

List of symbols

Symbol	Unit	Description
M	mol/L	Molarity
m	mol/kg	Molality
wt	–	Mass fraction
x	–	Mole fraction liquid phase
y	–	Mole fraction vapour phase
P _{tot}	kPa	Total pressure
P _{CO₂}	kPa	Partial Pressure of CO ₂
T	°C	Temperature
α _{CO₂}	–	CO ₂ -loading defined as: number of moles of CO ₂ over number of moles of amines in the solutions

(continued on next column)

Symbol	Unit	Description
[amine]	M	Molar concentration of amine
c _p	$\frac{kJ}{mol \cdot K}$	Liquid heat capacity.
H _{excess}	$\frac{kJ}{mol}$	Excess molar enthalpy of mixing
k	$\frac{W}{m^2 \cdot K}$	Thermal Conductivity
k _{obs}	$\frac{1}{s}$	First order kinetics constant
k ₂	$\frac{m^3}{mol \cdot s}$	Second order kinetics constant
N _{CO₂}	$\frac{mol}{m^3 \cdot s}$	CO ₂ mole flux.
k _L	$\frac{m}{s}$	Liquid film mass-transfer coefficient
k _g	$\frac{m}{s}$	Gas film mass-transfer coefficient
H _{CO₂,solution}	kPa	Henry Constant of CO ₂
D _{CO₂}	$\frac{m^2}{s}$	Diffusion coefficient of CO ₂ in liquid phase
K _{ov}	$\frac{m}{s}$	Overall gas mass transfer coefficient
LMPD	kPa	Logarithmic Mean Pressure Difference
SRD	$\frac{GJ}{ton \ of \ CO_2}$	Specific Reboiler Duty
L/G	$\frac{kg}{kg}$	Liquid-Gas ratio
aq.	–	Aqueous
BOD	–	biological oxygen demand
CAPEX	–	Capital expenditure
CCGT	–	combined cycle gas turbine
CHP	–	combined-heat-and-power
DCC	–	Direct Contact Cooler
EC ₅₀	–	effective concentration inhibiting 50 % growth
FPD	–	Freezing point depression
FTIR	–	Fourier-transform infrared detection
GCMS	–	gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry
HSS	–	heat stable salts
IC	–	ion chromatography
ICR	–	Ion cyclotron resonance
IMR-MS	–	ion-molecule reaction mass spectrometer
LCMS	–	liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry
LD ₅₀	–	lethal concentration causing 50 % mortality
LOQ	–	Limit of quantification.
MS	–	Mass spectrometry
NMPC	–	nonlinear model predictive control
PP	–	powerplant
ppb	–	parts per billion
ppm	–	parts per million
PTR-QMS	–	proton-transfer-reaction quadrupole mass spectrometer
PTR-MS-TOF	–	proton-transfer-reaction time-of-flight mass spectrometer
PZAS TM	–	Piperazine Advanced Flash Stripper
RFCC	–	residual fluid catalytic cracker
TD ₅₀	–	median toxic dose
ThOD	–	theoretical oxygen demand
TRL	–	technology readiness level
vol.	–	Volume

Chemical abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name
AAEA	2-amino-N-(2-aminoethyl)-acetamide
AEAAC	N-(2-Aminoethyl)glycine
AEHA	N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-hydroxyacetamide
AEAFD	Formamide, N-(2-aminoethyl)
AEAEPZ	N1-[2-(1-piperazinyl)ethyl]-1,2-ethanediamine
AEAEPZ urea	1-[2-(1-Piperazinyl)ethyl]-2-imidazolidinone
AEHA	N-(2-aminoethyl)-2-hydroxy-acetamide
AEI	1-(2-Aminoethyl)imidazolidin-2-one
AEP	n-(2-aminoethyl) piperazine
PolyAEP	4-[2-(1-Piperazinyl)ethyl]-1-piperazineethanamine
AMP	2-amino-2-methyl-propanolamine
AMPAMP	2-[(2-amino-2-methylpropyl)amino]-2-methyl-1-propanol
AMP-NO ₂	2-methyl-2-(nitroamino)-1-propanol
AMP urea	N,N'-bis(2-hydroxy-1,1-dimethylethyl)-urea
APAE	N ¹ -(2-Aminoethyl)-N ² -[2-[[2-(1-piperazinyl)ethyl]amino]ethyl]-1,2-ethanediamine
APEE	N ¹ ,N ² -Bis(2-aminoethyl)-N ¹ -[2-(1-piperazinyl)ethyl]-1,2-ethanediamine

(continued on next page)

Abbreviation	Name
BHMU	1,3-bis(N-hydroxymethyl)urea
CBP	1,1'-carbonylbis piperazine / 1,2- carbonylbis PZ urea
DAEP	1,4-di(2-aminoethyl) piperazine
DEBP	1,1'-(1,2-dioxo-1,2- ethanediy)bis piperazine
DFP	1-4-diformyl piperazine
DHMEDA	N,N'-di(2- hydroxymethyl) EDA
DMHTBI	4,4-dimethyl-1-hydroxytertiobutyl-2-imidazolidinone
DMO	4,4-dimehylloxazolidine
DMOZD	4,4-dimethyl-2-oxazolidinone
DMP	N,N'-dimethyl piperazine
DNPZ	dinitrosopiperazine
EDA	ethylenediamine
EPZ	2,5-piperazinedione
FPZ	1-formyl piperazine
HEP	1-(2-Hydroxyethyl) piperazine
HIEA	2-(1H-imidazol-1-yl)ethanamine
HMTA	Methenamine
LUT	2,4-lutidine
MEA	ethanolamine
MNPZ	N-nitrosopiperazine
MPM	α -methyl-1-piperazinemethanol
MPZ	N-methyl piperazine
NDELA	N-nitrosodiethanolamine
NDMA	N-nitrosodimethylamine
N-formyl AMP	N-(1-hydroxy-2-methylpropan-2-yl)formamide
N-methyl AMP	2-methyl-2-(methylamino)-1-propanol
N-nitroso AMP	1-Propanol, 2-methyl-2-(methylnitrosoamino)-
OPZ	2-Piperazinone
PEP	1,1'-(1,2-ethanediy)bis-piperazine
PEPA	N-[2-(1-Piperazinyl)ethyl]-1- piperazineethanamine
PZ	piperazine
PZ-NO ₂	1-Nitropiperazine
PZOH	Piperazin-2-ol
TEDA	Triethylenediamine
TMOZD	3,4,4-trimethyl-2-oxazolidinone

Declaration of interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Diego Morlando: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Vanja Buvik:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Asmira Delic:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Ardi Hartono:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Hallvard F. Svendsen:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Hanne M. Kvamsdal:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Eirik F. da Silva:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Hanna K. Knuutila:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Supplementary materials

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